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Entwicklung eines multispektralen Durchflusszellensensors zum Online-Monitoring von Mikroalgenkulturen

Development of a multi-wavelength flow-through cell sensor for on-line monitoring of microalgae cultivations

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Abstract

The biotechnological use of microalgae can contribute to the shift towards a sustainable economy due to its potential for biofuel production, pigments, healthy foods, and wastewater treatment. For the efficient and thus competitive use of microalgae, real-time monitoring of the biological process variables is essential to keep the culture permanently in an optimal condition. Since it is very difficult to measure biological process variables like morphology and intracellular metabolites directly in real-time, the use of software sensors based on intensive data processing is a promising option. However, the development and operation of these software sensors requires large amounts of meaningful and versatile real-time data on microalgae cultures. Here we present an on-line multi-wavelength optical flow-through cell sensor for real-time monitoring of microalgae. It has a modular design, enables multi-angle scattered light measurement and uses three LEDs with wavelengths of 780 nm, 690 nm and 505 nm for the indirect estimation of biomass concentration, chlorophyll concentration and carotenoid concentration. We demonstrated that the sensor setup enables low-noise and stable measurement of transmission (0°) and side scatter (90°) during three-week cultivation of *Chlorella vulgaris* in the bypass of a photobioreactor. We found that the sensor signals are directly related to the absorbance of an off-line spectrophotometer. This allows the sensor to qualitatively monitor biomass and specific pigment concentration. Our results demonstrate that the presented on-line multi-wavelength optical flow-through cell sensor can thus provide a real-time data basis for the development and operation of sophisticated software sensors for monitoring of biological process variables in microalgae cultures.

Task

Microalgae are well-known photosynthetic microbes used as cell factories for the production of relevant biotechnological compounds (e.g. pigments, unsaturated fatty acids) and environmental applications (e.g. wastewater treatment, lipids for biofuel). Despite these outstanding characteristics, industrial scale production of microalgae is still at an early stage of development. Moreover, the economically viable support of the sustainable large-scale production of microalgae at the present state of technology is a challenge.

One important bottleneck in this support is the lack of suitable on-line sensors for the reliable monitoring of biological parameters, mostly concentration of intracellular components, in microalgae bioprocesses. The application of software sensors, i.e., estimators based on model and data driven process models, using physical signal inputs of multiple sensors could complement the on-line monitoring as it allows the estimation of the desired biological process variables in real or almost-real time, which are often hidden in the spectroscopic data and only indirectly accessible.

The aim of this master thesis is the development of an optical flow-through sensor for on-line UV-VIS-IR measurements using multiple LEDs. Based on literature research and experiments, a concept of the sensor will be developed and the sensor housing can be manufactured by the support of additive manufacturing/rapid prototyping techniques. This self-constructed sensor will be connected to a bypass of an existing photobioreactor. With this setup the sensors functionality will be evaluated by monitoring the cultivation of microalgae with the perspective to use this sensor concept for the development of software sensors to estimate the biological process variables of microalgae cultures in future studies.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Theoretical background	3
2.1	Optical measurement methods used in biotechnology	3
2.1.1	UV-Vis spectroscopy	4
2.1.2	Turbidity measurement	7
2.2	Microalgae: photosynthetic microorganisms	8
2.2.1	Photosynthesis and pigments	9
2.2.2	Biotechnological production with <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	10
2.3	Monitoring of biological process variables in microalgae cultivations with optical sensors	12
2.3.1	Measurement principles – in-line, on-line, at-line, off-line	12
2.3.2	Methods for measuring microalgae biomass and pigment con- centration	13
3	Results and discussion	18
3.1	Analysis of <i>C. vulgaris</i> shake flask cultures with off-line spectrophotometry	18
3.1.1	Absorbance spectrum of <i>C. vulgaris</i> by pigment absorption	18
3.1.2	Temporal change of the absorbance spectrum of <i>C. vulgaris</i>	21
3.2	Sensor development	25
3.2.1	Measurement concept - light source and angle	26
3.2.2	Design of the flow-through cell	28
3.2.3	Design of the sensor housing	30
3.2.4	Design of measurement software	37
3.3	Sensor evaluation with chemicals	39
3.3.1	Evaluation with ink	40
3.3.2	Evaluation with formazin	46
3.4	Sensor evaluation with <i>C. vulgaris</i> in the bypass of a photobioreactor	51
3.4.1	On-line approximation of biomass concentration	51
3.4.2	On-line approximation of pigment content	60
4	Conclusion and outlook	66
4.1	Conclusion	66
4.2	Outlook	68
5	Appendix	70
5.1	Methods	70

5.2 Materials	80
List of abbreviations and symbols	83
List of Figures	86
List of Tables	88
Bibliography	89

1 Introduction

Due to climate change and the extinction of species, mankind is facing very serious challenges. Many industries are based on the use of fossil fuels whose combustion enriches the atmosphere with the greenhouse gas carbon dioxide (CO₂) and take more resources from nature than is sustainably [1, 2]. Therefore, it is essential to develop new eco-friendly processes. An opportunity for this is the industrial use of microalgae in the context of the circular and sustainable bioeconomy [3]. Microalgae are fast-growing microorganisms that extract large amounts of CO₂ from the environment through photosynthesis using light energy and store it in their biomass more efficiently than higher plants [4, 5]. Their flexible metabolism allows them to accumulate many substances useful to human health, making microalgae biotechnologically interesting for the production of high-value products. For example, microalgae are used to produce nutritional supplements due to their high content of unsaturated fatty acids. Another use is processing certain ingredients into pharmaceuticals to take advantage of their therapeutic effects [1, 5]. However, microalgae also offer the potential to be used for low-value-added products and processes [6]. These include, for example, the production of bulk chemicals, commodities for aquaculture feeds, biofertilizers, biofuels, and applications for CO₂ capture and wastewater treatment [6]. In recent years, the production of biofuel by microalgae has attracted attention. This is because with some microalgae species it is possible to produce more than ten times as much lipids per area required for biofuel production as with the most effective crops [4, 7, 8, 9]. It is also possible to cultivate microalgae without competing with other important land uses such as agriculture or forestation [10, 11]. This is because some species can be cultivated in arid regions such as deserts and grow in saline and brackish water [11, 12, 13]. In addition, the production of microalgae can be coupled with their usefulness for wastewater or exhaust gas treatment [6].

However, this great potential faces the problem that the large scale production of microalgae is not efficient enough and the downstream processing costs are too high. As

a result, low-value-added products from microalgae such as biofuel are currently failing to establish themselves on the market compared to cheaper conventional products [5, 6, 13]. To increase efficiency and thereby reduce costs, it is essential to enable year-round, stable cultivation of microalgae under optimal conditions and to reduce manpower [6]. This can be achieved through automated monitoring and control [14, 15, 16]. The monitoring required for this should be in real-time and non-invasive [17]. Optical sensors meet these requirements because they are fast, simple, and accurate [18, 19]. Therefore, a current object of research is to develop an optical sensor, that can be used in the production of low-value-added products due to its low price and robustness, in order to collect as much information as possible about the state of the microalgae culture in real time [19, 20, 21]. However, information about the state of the microalgae, as well as the concentration of intracellular components, can only be measured indirectly [17]. Therefore, it is a challenge to trace the measurement signal back to individual biological variables [17]. Within the project, in which this work is integrated, it is attempted to monitor the difficult-to-access information about the condition of the microalgae with the help of different real-time sensor signals via data processing. For this purpose, the aim of this work is to develop an on-line flow-through cell optical sensor that can collect relevant data about microalgae cultures in real-time and in a non-invasive manner. Thus, this represents an important component of the software sensor-based monitoring and control system for the cultivation of microalgae.

2 Theoretical background

2.1 Optical measurement methods used in biotechnology

In biotechnology, optical sensors are used to obtain information about the properties of biological samples [17]. The interaction of electromagnetic radiation with the molecules in the sample is used as the measuring principle. Electromagnetic radiation has both wave and particle properties and the interaction with the sample depends on both the properties of the molecules and the type of electromagnetic radiation [22]. An important quantity for characterizing electromagnetic radiation is its wavelength λ [22]. Depending on the wavelength, electromagnetic radiation is classified into different types of radiation [23]. In the context of this thesis ultra-violet radiation, visible light and near infrared radiation have a special relevance. The definition of these three types of electromagnetic radiation based on their wavelength in accordance to the International Commission on Illumination is shown in Figure 2.1 [23].

Figure 2.1: Ranges of electromagnetic radiation defined by their wavelength according to [23]. Adapted from [24].

The International Commission on Illumination defines electromagnetic radiation with wavelengths from 100 nm to 400 nm as ultraviolet radiation (UV). The range from 315 nm to 400 nm is called UV-A. The part of electromagnetic radiation which is visible to our eyes (VIS) starts at about 400 nm which we perceive as violet. The range of visible light passes over blue, green and yellow and ends at about 780 nm

with the color red. The limits of the visible range are not precise because they depend on individual factors of the human eye [25]. Electromagnetic radiation with longer wavelengths is hardly or not visible anymore and is called infrared radiation (IR). The part of the infrared range, that is close to the visible light is called near infrared or IR-A. IR-A radiation ranges from 780 nm to 1400 nm. [23]

To analyze the different phenomena that occur from the interaction between light and matter in the context of an optical sensor, it is worthwhile to imagine the behavior of light in a cuvette used for routine spectrophotometric analysis. A schematic upper view from the cuvette is shown in Figure 2.2. When light enters the interior of the cuvette, part of the light can pass through the sample unhindered. This behavior is called transmission. However, another part of the light interacts with the molecules in the sample. This part of the light does not emerge unhindered on the other side of the sample. This underlying phenomenon is called attenuation. Attenuation is based on two different interactions of light with matter. On the one hand, absorption can occur. In this case, the light excites certain structures of the molecules and the transferred light energy is dissipated as heat, emitted by fluorescence with a different wavelength or converted into chemical energy [16, 22]. [26]

While on the other hand, light scattering occurs, whereby the light leads to charge carrier separation at the molecular level, thus creating dipoles [27]. The dipoles then emit light with the same wavelengths as the exciting light, but in a different direction than the exciting light. The spatial direction depends on the molecular environment of the dipole [27]. For a radiation angle between 0° and 90° one speaks of forward scatter, for 90° of side scatter and for 90° to 180° of backscatter [28]. The effects of light scattering and absorption are shown in Figure 2.2 where I_0 is the intensity of the incoming light and I_T is the intensity of transmitted light, attenuated by particles or molecules. $I_S(\theta)$ is the scattered light measured in angle θ . Scatter effects play a minor role as long as the particle size is small compared to the wavelengths [29].

2.1.1 UV-Vis spectroscopy

UV-Vis spectroscopy is a widely used measurement method in chemistry and biology for determining concentrations by absorption [30, 31]. A sample is irradiated with light of a defined intensity I_0 and wavelength λ and the intensity of the transmitted light I_T , as already presented in Figure 2.2, is measured. If this intensity is set in relation to the

Figure 2.2: Interactions of light with the particle of a sample inside a spectrophotometer cuvette shown from the upper view.

incident intensity, the so-called transmittance T is obtained, as shown in the formula 2.1 [29]. Since it is often difficult to measure the intensity of the incident light in a fixed experimental setup and the influence of reflection needs to be minimized, a different reference point is needed. In practice, this is done by dividing the transmittance of the sample T by the transmittance $T_{c=0}$ of a reference solution that does not contain the analyte, for example medium or solvent. As shown in formula 2.2, by this procedure the intensity of the incident light is cancelled out [19, 32, 33]. The inverse of the transmittance is called opacity O and is shown in formula 2.3 [34]. Therefore, the opacity is a measure for how much light is attenuated compared to the blank.

$$T = \frac{I_T}{I_0} \quad (2.1)$$

$$T' = \frac{T}{T_{c=0}} = \frac{\frac{I_T}{I_0}}{\frac{I_{T,c=0}}{I_0}} = \frac{I_T}{I_{T,c=0}} \quad (2.2)$$

$$O = \frac{1}{T'} \quad (2.3)$$

Lambert-Beer law

If the particles in the sample are very small compared to the wavelength, scattering can be neglected and in the approximation only absorption leads to attenuation [29]. In this case the so-called Lambert-Beer law can be applied. It represents the relation between the product of concentration of a substance c , path length l and decadic wavelength-dependent absorption coefficient $\varepsilon(\lambda)$ on one side and the decadic logarithm of the opacity on the other side. This negative logarithmic term is called absorbance and has the formula symbol A . The Lambert-Beer law is shown in equation 2.4 [29].

$$A(\lambda) := \log_{10} O(\lambda) = c \cdot l \cdot \varepsilon(\lambda) \quad (2.4)$$

This relation has the benefit that absorbance is linear proportional to the concentration as long as the product from path length l and wavelength-dependent absorption coefficient $\varepsilon(\lambda)$ remains constant [29]. By that the relative changes of the concentration can directly be measured via the absorbance at a specific wavelength.

The scope of the Lambert-Beer law is limited. The reason for this is that the decadic absorption coefficient $\varepsilon(\lambda)$ can no longer be assumed to be constant at higher concentrations, but decreases with increasing concentration [29]. Thus, the absorbance at higher concentrations is no longer linear with respect to concentration. Instead, the increase in absorbance flattens out with increasing concentration [29]. Furthermore, there are deviations from the Lambert-Beer law if, in addition to absorption, scattering is no longer negligible [35]. This is for example the case if larger particles like cells are measured [28]. In this case, the term attenuance is proposed by the IUPAC instead of absorbance to clarify the different physical background between the two concepts [36]. However, in some scientific literature, the term absorbance or optical density is also used when cells are examined that cause both, scattering and absorption [19, 32, 37]. Therefore, in the same manner the term absorbance instead of attenuance will be used in this work.

There are more sophisticated models that predict the propagation of light in absorbing and scattering suspensions depending on the suspension properties such as the complex index of refraction of the particles, the particle shape and the number of particles. These are based, for example, on the three-dimensional conservation of light energy [38, 39, 40]. However, the solution of these integro-differential models is computationally very demanding and the determination of the parameters is complex [35]. Therefore, the mechanistic modeling of simultaneously scattering and absorbing particle suspensions is not further discussed in this thesis. Instead, as widely used in the literature, the much simpler Lambert-Beer law is also applied to scattering particle suspensions [26].

2.1.2 Turbidity measurement

Turbidity measurement is a widely used technique for the quantification of the particles in suspension, for example, for the detection of sediment content in water [28]. Depending on the angle of measurement two methods, turbidimetry and nephelometry, are distinguished [28]. For turbidimetry measurements the transmitted light is measured, that means in the direction of 0° as shown in Figure 2.2. Turbidimetry can be seen as a special case of spectrometry where only one wavelength is used. Furthermore, the aim of turbidimetry is not to measure the attenuation caused only by absorption but caused also by light scattering [28]. The Lambert-Beer law is also applied for turbidity measurements although it is error-prone in this case. [26, 28]. Nephelometry measurements are performed in an angle higher than 0° such that a part of the scattered light is measured directly [28]. The standard calibration of turbidity measurement devices is done with a suspension of water and formazin. Formazin is a polymer, which is insoluble in water and which is prepared by mixing of hydrazine sulphate and hexamethylenetetramine [28]. The concentration of formazin produced by the defined method of preparation is expressed in the unit NTU (nephelometric turbidity units) [41].

Depending on the measurement angle, the measured signal responds with different sensitivity to changes of the particle concentration. Signal characteristics at high particle concentrations may differ as well. For example, at low particle densities a side scatter measurement in 90° has a more sensitive response than a backscatter measurement. Anyway, at high particle densities the side scatter measurement is not advisable any-

more. The reason is that with increasing particle concentration the measured side scattered light reaches a maximum and then starts to decrease, because of the attenuation in the optically dense liquid it has to pass. In contrast, the backscatter measurement has an advantage at high concentrations, because light that is backscattered in the first molecular layers is less strongly attenuated. Therefore, at high concentrations, the backscatter signal reaches a saturation. This leads to a less sensitive response of the backscatter signal to concentration changes. However, in contrast to the side scatter signal, the relationship between the backscatter signal and the particle concentration remains unique. [41, 42]

Besides turbidimetry and nephelometry, scatter light is also measured in flow cytometry. In flow cytometry single cells are irradiated with a laser and, depending on the angular distribution of the scattered light, conclusions about the cells can be made. The forward scatter is a proxy for the size and the refractive index of the cells [43]. There is more light scattered in the forward than in the sideward or backward direction [27]. The side scatter signal is rather dependent on the internal structure, shape and cross section of cells, and backscatter is also more sensitive to differentiate particle populations by size [43, 44].

2.2 Microalgae: photosynthetic microorganisms

Algae are classified as photosynthetic organisms which may not follow the same evolutionary line as plants, containing members of prokaryotic Bacteria and eukaryotic Plantae, Chromista, and Protozoa [22]. They are distinguished from terrestrial plants (*embryophytes*) by the degree of differentiation of their cells. That means plants have many different macroscopic compartments like roots and leaves and stems while algae mostly do not have any. Unlike terrestrial plants, algae do not form embryos [22]. Algae are divided between microalgae and macroalgae. Macroalgae are multicellular, macroscopic, and photosynthetic organisms. If they live in oceans they are also called seaweed and can be up to 60 m long [45]. Microalgae are fast growing microscopic photosynthetic unicellular microorganisms, either eukaryotic or prokaryotic (e.g. cyanobacteria) [46]. The smallest known microalgae is the unicellular *Micromonas pusilla* with a size of about 1 μm [45]. Microalgae form a diverse group of microorganisms of which more than 72500 species are already described [5, 47]. Microalgae species are divided into 16 classes, of which the most important for biotechnological

application are cyanobacteria, green algae and diatoms [47]. Their diversity is also reflected by the different habitats they populate. Some microalgae species are living in saltwater or salt lakes, some are living in freshwater and some are living at places exposed to the atmosphere [22]. If microalgae are suspended in water, they are called phytoplankton. This phytoplankton has a huge value for the worldwide ecosystems since it produces about 50 % of the oxygen that is emitted to the atmosphere from all sources. Furthermore, phytoplankton is an important base of the marine food chain [22].

2.2.1 Photosynthesis and pigments

Most microalgae are photoautotroph, that means that they get their entire energy for growth by their photosynthetic apparatus and use CO_2 as carbon source [22].

The oxygenic photosynthesis is a sequence of redox reactions which can be divided into light reactions and dark reactions as shown in Figure 2.3. The light reactions take place in the chloroplasts' thylakoids and provide high energy molecules (e.g. ATP) and reductive power (e.g. NADPH_2). These molecules are then used in the dark reactions for the reduction of carbon dioxide to carbohydrates. [48]

Figure 2.3: Oxygenic photosynthesis grouped by light and dark reactions [48].

In order to capture light in the chloroplasts, microalgae employ the light absorption properties of pigments. Microalgae are using different compositions of pigments depending on the light availability in their natural habitat. For example, some pigments serve to absorb light at greater depths, while others protect the photosynthetic apparatus from damage caused by excessive light intensities [22]. The photosynthetic apparatus contains a light-harvesting antenna in which protein-pigment complexes funnel light energy via electron transfer to the reaction center of the light reaction. Different pigments can be found in this antenna depending on evolution and habitat of the microalgae species. These pigments can be grouped into three major classes - chloro-

phylls, carotenoids and phycobilins [47]. Chlorophylls do not absorb green light and therefore they appear green to the human eye. Chlorophyll a is present in the antenna and core reaction center of all oxygenic phototrophs. Furthermore, Chlorophyll b, c and d can occur in the light-harvesting antenna to extend the range of usable wavelengths. Carotenoids are another class of pigments which absorb light in the blue and green area and thus appear yellow orange. Carotenoids fulfill two roles. On the one side they extend the absorption range of the light-harvesting antenna and on the other side they protect the photosynthetic system from excess radiation and reactive oxygen species. Furthermore, some microalgae species overproduce secondary carotenoids like xanthophylls (astaxanthin and canthaxanthin) if they are exposed to physiological stress [48]. Besides chlorophylls and carotenoids, phycobilins are also main pigments mostly present in cyanobacteria and red algae [48]. [22]

2.2.2 Biotechnological production with *Chlorella vulgaris*

C. vulgaris was the microalgae selected for the development of the on-line optical flow-through cell sensor. It is a eucaryotic microalgae and belongs to the class of green microalgae [47]. *C. vulgaris* is round shaped and has a diameter of about 2 μm - 10 μm and lives in freshwater [49]. It contains high amounts of the chlorophyll a (1-2% of dry mass) and chlorophyll b and the carotenoid lutein. Furthermore, it contains carotene, antheraxanthin, violaxanthin and neoxanthin, astaxanthin, cantaxanthin, pheophythin a and zeaxanthin [5, 47, 49, 50, 51]. Pheophytin can be formed as a consequence of chlorophyll a degradation during growth or harsh conditions [5]. Moreover *C. vulgaris* has a high protein content (40 - 60 % of dry weight) [47]. Besides proteins, *C. vulgaris* can accumulate lipids (14-22 %), for example essential fatty acids, and also minerals and vitamins [4, 5, 47].

C. vulgaris is fast growing and relatively resistant towards harsh conditions which makes it interesting for biotechnological applications [47]. *C. vulgaris* is used in various biotechnological applications, due to the previously described richness of metabolites useful for humans and industry. A major field of application is the food industry. Because of the high protein content, and the production of essential fatty acids and vitamins, *C. vulgaris* is produced as a food or dietary supplement [5, 52]. Additionally, in animal agriculture it is used as fodder supplement among other reasons because of the coloring properties of the carotenoids. Another application field is the produc-

tion of drugs. For this purpose, certain metabolites of *C. vulgaris* are purified and used in pharmaceuticals due to their immunomodulatory and anticancer properties [5]. Furthermore, there are industrial applications where large quantities of *C. vulgaris* are produced with lower quality requirements. These include, for example, wastewater treatment, where *C. vulgaris* primarily excels in the reduction of ammonium [53]. Moreover *C. vulgaris* can be used for the production of third generation biofuels which do not compete with food or arable lands [10]. Because of high production costs and the lack of ensured sustainability benefits this technique still needs research [5]. Due to this versatile usability of microalgae, the concept of biorefinery is very interesting. In a biorefinery, an attempt is made to link various applications within one process chain of separation operations with the intention of making the production more profitable [17].

Cultivation conditions can have a strong influence on biotechnological products of *C. vulgaris* [5]. For example, the lipid content increases under nutrient limitation conditions (e.g. nitrate limitation), while protein content increases when nitrogen is supplemented [5]. Furthermore, it was reported that the carbon source affects the biochemical components produced by *C. vulgaris* [52]. Therefore, different cultivation methods are used in order to optimize the production of the respective target product [5].

Because of their broad spectrum of products, several techniques for the cultivation of microalgae exist. The most common and cheapest cultivation technique is the use of open pond systems which have no physical barrier to the environment [5, 20]. Open pond systems can be created using naturally occurring water sources such as lakes or lagoons. Alternatively, artificial water reservoirs can be provided, in which, for example, wastewater is reused. Despite the advantage of low complexity and usage of natural light the use of open systems also leads to problems. For example, contamination with other microorganisms and unstable environmental conditions such as fluctuating temperature and radiation lead to lower biomass yields [5]. Alternatively, closed systems like photobioreactors can be used. They are physically separated from the environment and thus deliver a controlled environment with stable conditions [14]. The use of a photobioreactor allows the cultivation of less robust microalgae species, as well as the production of pharmaceutical products with high quality requirements. However, photobioreactors have the disadvantage that both the energy requirement for artificial light and the implementation of sterilization processes increase production costs [5]. Besides that, variances in the design of the reactor the microalgae metabolic

features influence the production process. According to the energy source and carbon source used by microalgae there are three variations of growth that could be observed: autotrophic, heterotrophic, and myxotrophic [5]. If the microalgae are growing only with energy from light it is called an autotrophic. If the microalgae use organic carbon sources without the use of light one speaks of a heterotrophic culture. And if the energy is provided by light as well as organic carbon sources the cultivation is called mixotrophic. Mixotrophic cultivations are used to reduce biomass losses when no light is available. This is also the case for high biomass concentrations where the microalgae shade each other. Mixotropic growth is used for example for wastewater treatment. [5, 54]

2.3 Monitoring of biological process variables in microalgae cultivations with optical sensors

For the biotechnological use of microalgae presented in Chapter 2.2.2 it is essential to be able to control the production process [6]. For this purpose, the process must be monitored [14, 19].

2.3.1 Measurement principles – in-line, on-line, at-line, off-line

There are different principles for monitoring a process. They can be categorized in four groups by the terms in-line, on-line, at-line and off-line depending on the physical location of measurement [55]. In-line measurements are *in situ* which means 'in the site' and the measurement is done directly in the main process stream. Compared to that, on-line measurements are not performed in the main process stream but in a bypass, through which a part of the main process stream is redirected. At-line measurements are done close to the location of sampling which means for example in the same lab. But in contrast to on-line and in-line measurement, at-line measurements require manual work for its performance. For off-line measurements manual work is needed too, and additionally the location of measurement is further away like for example in another laboratory building. There are also suggestions to define every measurement as an off-line measurement if it is not in real-time. Real-time means that the duration

of the measurement process is short enough such that the measured value is still representative for the state of the system. This is achieved if the system changes slowly compared to measurement time delay. [55]

Optimal process control and automatization have the potential to increase the product quality as well as the monetary balance of the process [19]. Therefore, real-time information is needed to keep the state of the microalgae always close to the optimal conditions [19]. Furthermore, it is desirable to avoid manual sampling in order to reduce costs and the risk of contamination. On-line and in-line sensors can fulfill these demands [17].

2.3.2 Methods for measuring microalgae biomass and pigment concentration

In the cultivation of microalgae, many process variables affect cultivation performance. Therefore, the availability of information on these variables is crucial for the analysis and control of the process [6, 20]. Process variables can be assigned to three groups which are the physical variables, the chemical variables, and the biological variables [17, 21]. The physical variables include, for example, temperature and mixing intensity. The group of chemical variables includes, for example, all extracellular concentrations like dissolved nutrients, pH-value and extracellular products. And the group of biological variables includes for example the concentration of biomass as well as the morphology of cells, concentration of all intracellular components and the physiological state of the microalgae [17, 21]. For physical and chemical variables many on-line and in-line sensors already exist since the technology is used in many fields of the biochemical industry [17]. However, for many biological process variables only standardized off-line analyzers exist because the measurement of the biological process variables is complex and their field of application is smaller [17].

Measurement of microalgae biomass concentration

The biomass concentration is the basic biological variable that needs to be tracked in any microbial cultivation [17, 20]. It is needed, for example, to determine the optimal time for harvesting. Furthermore, it is the key control variable of continuous cultures

[15]. The standard method to determine the biomass concentration is the measurement of dry cell weight. Unfortunately, this is a labor intensive off-line method and cannot be used for real-time applications [19, 20]. An alternative is the use of turbidity measurements, either via turbidimetry with an UV-Vis-spectrophotometer or with a nephelometer [15, 19, 32]. In the case of microalgae, the impact of absorption by pigments on the proxy for the biomass has to be minimized, because the pigment content can change independently from the biomass during the cultivation [32]. To avoid this problem light sources should be used which do not emit light in the absorption range of the pigments to improve the accuracy of biomass estimation [19, 32]. Nevertheless, even for turbidimetry measurements with 750 nm, where no absorption by pigments occurs, the correlation between biomass concentration and standard absorbance can vary by about 30 % during the cultivation [32]. This error can be reduced by using samples taken at different cultivation times for calibration [32]. There are already on-line sensors with industrial standard available which can be used to measure the turbidimetry or nephelometry to measure the biomass concentration [7, 15, 17, 19, 20, 41, 56]. Unfortunately, there are only some suitable for high biomass concentrations and have a relative high cost [57].

Measurement of pigment concentration

In the case of microalgae, another important biological variable is the intracellular pigment concentration. As already described in Chapter 2.2.2, in some processes the pigments are the main product and need to be monitored for process optimization. Furthermore, the pigment content contains information about the physiological state of the microalgae and the health of the culture [19]. For example, as described in Chapter 2.2.1, the concentration of some xanthophylls may depend on physiological stress to which the microalgae are exposed [48]. Furthermore, changes in the pigment content can be used to detect the presence of a contamination with a foreign microorganism. Especially the contamination with non-photosynthetic organisms is reflected by a decrease of the relative pigment content per biomass [32]. The standard methods to measure the pigment concentration are high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), spectrophotometry or fluorometry [48, 58, 59, 60]. These methods can be used to measure the concentration of pigments dissolved in solvents. However, this *in vitro* measurement has the disadvantage that it can hardly be transferred to real-time applications [38]. Spectrophotometry and fluorometry can also be used to

measure microalgae *in vivo* [19, 60]. Spectroscopy has shown to be useful for real-time measurements for indication of absorbance, turbidity and fluorescence because it is non-invasive and fast [19]. Nevertheless, if whole cells are measured, the signal is more strongly influenced by scattering which is, as discussed in Chapter 2.1.2, affected by the morphology of the cells [40].

There also exist fluorescence sensors which can measure chlorophyll contents from 0 to $500 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and use a turbidity correction between 0 to 200 FTU and could theoretically be implemented into a bypass [61, 62]. However, these sensors are designed for ecological research to detect for example algae blooms. In industrial applications the algae biomass concentration is much higher than in the natural environment which also results in much higher chlorophyll contents [19]. Griffiths et al. found a pigment concentration of about $9000 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in *C. vulgaris*, which is almost 20-fold of the suitable (linear) range of the industrial sensors for ecology applications [32]. The applicability of fluorescence-based sensors in high turbidity conditions is also a problem for sensor prototypes which are explicitly designed for the microalgae production [14]. Furthermore, these industrial sensors are not suited for high throughput productions of low value products like lipids for biofuel because of their higher price [19].

State of the art on-line and in-line optical sensors for real-time monitoring of pigment content or biomass concentrations in microalgae cultivations

In order to make the measurement of biomass concentration of microalgae cultures simpler, more robust and as less expensive, new concepts for optical sensors have been developed in recent years [19, 20]. These are often based on the use of multiple light sources with different wavelengths. LEDs (light emitting diodes) or laser diodes are frequently used as light sources for this purpose. In some cases, this is an attempt to draw conclusions about the pigment concentration in addition to the biomass, or at least to collect additional information about the condition of the algae [14, 19]. Some sensor systems developed in recent years are listed in table 2.1 and are presented in more detail in the following. Jia et al. developed an on-line sensor system using three laser diodes with 650 nm and 685 nm and 780 nm to estimate the biomass concentration. They fitted the optical depth of all three wavelengths to the dry weight and found the best correlation with 780 nm. Furthermore, they tracked the ratio of the optical depths at 650 nm and 685 nm to 780 nm to find an indication for the change of the chlorophyll content [19]. Barbosa et al. used LEDs instead of laser diodes with 400 nm,

Table 2.1: State of the art optical sensors with multiple wavelengths for real-time monitoring of microalgae cultivations.

Light source: wavelength [nm]	Measurement principle	Target component	Comment	Reference
Laser diodes: 650, 685, 780	Attenuation	Biomass	Absorbance ratio for further information	[19]
LEDs: 400, 850, 940	Attenuation	Biomass	reference photodiode	[20]
LEDs: 470, 518, 630, 940	Attenuation	Cell count, adaptable	Neural network	[57]
LEDs: 680, 735	Attenuation, fluorescence	Biomass, chlorophyll a,	Fluorescence only for low densities	[14]
LED: 870	Attenuation, fluorescence	Biomass, chlorophyll	-	[63]
Halogen lamp	Attenuation	Carotenoids	Commercial spectrophotometer	[64]

850 nm and 940 nm. Furthermore, their sensor system contains a reference photodiode to measure the blank intensity of the LEDs [20]. Briassoulis et al. used LEDs with wavelengths of 470 nm, 518 nm, 630 nm and 940 nm. They fitted the measured voltage to the cell count by a neural network and gave the outlook that other parameters could be fitted with the flexible change of LED wavelengths [57]. Nedbal et al. developed a sensor system that uses an LED with 680 nm and a LED with 735 nm to estimate the chlorophyll content and cell count. By setting the absorbance at 680 nm in relation to the absorbance at 735 nm they could measure the start of the exponential growth phase. Furthermore, they used LEDs with 445 nm and 627 nm for fluorescence excitation, but could not use the fluorescence signal at higher biomass concentrations probably due to strong attenuation of excitation light [14]. Marxen et al. used a LED with 870 nm to estimate the biomass concentration and a LED with 630 nm to estimate the chlorophyll content by fluorescence [63]. In a different approach, Shao et al. did not use LEDs and photodiodes but a halogen light source and a commercial spectrophotometer. By processing the spectral data they could estimate the carotenoid content [64].

None of the sensors presented were used to simultaneously determine biomass concentration, chlorophyll content, and carotenoid content. Moreover, the biomass approximation of the sensors presented in Table 2.1 was based on transmission measurement.

None of the presented sensors used the nephelometric scattered light measurement method introduced in Chapter 2.1.2. This serves as a motivation for the development of an on-line optical multi-wavelength flow-through cell sensor, which attempts to exploit these capabilities and thereby further improve the monitoring options in microalgae biotechnology.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Analysis of *C. vulgaris* shake flask cultures with off-line spectrophotometry

In the development of the on-line flow-through multispectral sensor for the monitoring of certain microalgae, knowledge of the absorption spectra is crucial. Based on their specific spectra, wavelength ranges can be found whose use in the multispectral measurement provides informative insight into the condition of the microalgae. To collect information about the appearance of these spectra depending on the cultivation phase, shake flask cultivations of *C. vulgaris* were performed as described in the Appendix.

3.1.1 Absorbance spectrum of *C. vulgaris* by pigment absorption

First, the absorbance spectrum of an eight-day-old shake flask culture of *C. vulgaris* recorded with a UV-Vis spectrophotometer is discussed below and its course validated with *in vivo* data on pigment absorption from the literature. For this purpose, Figure 3.1 shows the measured absorbance spectrum of the sample (solid black line) including its absorbance peaks. These peaks can be explained by the absorption behavior of the pigments. Therefore, spectra of the specific absorption coefficient of living microalgae for different pigment classes are integrated in Figure 3.1 and represented by lines with symbols [38, 65].

The absorption coefficients of chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b are represented by black squares and red circles, respectively. The group of photoprotectant carotenoids (magenta diamonds) includes, among others, the photosynthetically non-active pigments

zeaxanthin and β -carotene, which are also present in *C. vulgaris* [65]. However, this group also includes the carotenoids diadinoxanthin and alloxanthin, which are not found in *C. vulgaris*. On the other hand, some carotenoids occurring in *C. vulgaris* are not included in the presented group of carotenoids. Therefore, the absorption peak positions of pigments also found in *C. vulgaris* measured *in vivo* by Méléder et al. are used [66]. These absorption peaks are shown as dashed vertical arrows in Figure 3.1. With regard to the spectra of the pigment absorption coefficients, it should also be mentioned that the absorption coefficient is a specific quantity, i.e., it is related to the pigment mass. Therefore, despite a large absorption coefficient, the influence of the pigment on the absorbance can be small if the pigment is present in only very small quantities.

When comparing the spectrum of the measured absorbance with the absorption coefficients from the literature, it can be clearly seen that the elevation of the measured absorbance between 400 nm and 525 nm can be explained by the superposition of the absorption of chlorophyll a and b as well as the carotenoids. In the absorbance between 400 nm and 525 nm two peaks can be detected. The peak at about 445 nm is primarily due to the absorbance of chlorophyll a. Méléder et al. reported an absorption maximum of chlorophyll a in living microalgae at 440 nm. In Figure 3.1 this peak is marked as a2. The second peak at 500 nm is caused by carotenoids, and Méléder et al. reported an absorption maxima of beta-carotene and lutein at 499 nm and 500 nm, respectively (c2, L).

As can be seen by comparison with the absorption coefficients in Figure 3.1, the second elevation of absorbance between 625 nm and 700 nm is determined only by the absorption of chlorophyll pigments. At 625 nm and 650 nm, weak peaks can be seen that can be attributed to chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b, respectively (a3, b) [66]. Furthermore, a pronounced maximum at 686 nm is observed in the absorbance spectrum of the sample. This also fits the expectations due to a peak of the absorption coefficient of chlorophyll a at about 675 nm, where Méléder et al. reported an absorption maxima of chlorophyll a at 671 nm and 683 nm (a4, a5). Other absorption maxima described in the literature cannot be clearly identified in the absorbance spectrum. These include the peak of pheophytin a at 407 nm (p1) and the peak of β -carotene at 466 nm (c1) [66, 67]. Comparing the spectra of absorbance and absorption coefficients, it is also noticeable that there are regions where pigments absorb little or no light. This includes the range between 575 nm and 625 nm and above 710 nm. However, the measured absorbance is significantly higher than zero in this range. This can be explained, as shown in Chapter 2.1, by the influence of light scattering, which overrides pure absorption

Figure 3.1: Comparison of off-line UV-Vis wavelength scan experiment with *in vivo* pigment absorption data from literature. Solid black line: experimental absorbance wavelength scan of diluted eight days old *C. vulgaris* shake flask culture with standard deviation over three samples (grayed area), black squares: chlorophyll a (Chl a) absorption coefficient, red circles: chlorophyll b (Chl b) absorption coefficient, magenta diamonds: photoprotectant carotenoids absorption coefficients [65]. Absorption peaks: Chl a (a1 - a5), Chl b (b), beta-carotene (c1, c2), lutein (L) and pheophytin (p1, p2) [66].

when studying cells with UV-Vis spectroscopy [26].

From the preceding comparison with values from the literature, it can be concluded that the absorption spectrum measured with the UV-Vis spectrophotometer can be explained by the interplay of scattering and absorption, and therefore the applied methodology provides reasonable results.

3.1.2 Temporal change of the absorbance spectrum of *C. vulgaris*

During batch cultivation, the cultivation conditions, such as substrate content, change, leading to different growth phases and physiological states of microalgae. For the development of an on-line flow-through multispectral sensor it is very important to know how the absorbance spectrum reflects this change of state. For this purpose, the results for two shake flask cultivations of *C. vulgaris* started at different time points are discussed below. The two shake flask cultivations are distinguished hereafter by the designations *Flask A* and *Flask B*.

The absorbance spectra of diluted samples from *Flask A* and *Flask B* were measured with the spectrophotometer at different times of cultivation and are shown in Figure 3.2. To compare the individual measurement time points of the two cultures with each other, the specific absorbance, i.e. absorbance per biomass, is needed. Assuming that the absorbance at 780 nm is linear to the biomass, the measured wavelength-dependent absorbance is divided by the absorbance at 780 nm. The normalized absorbance calculated in this way is plotted in Figure 3.2 versus wavelength for different cultivation durations. In Figure 3.2 a) the result for *Flask A* is shown. The main peaks of chlorophyll a identified in Figure 3.1 at about a 445 nm and 680 nm and of the carotenoids at about 500 nm can also be detected on all other days, as shown in 3.2 a). However, the normalized absorbance changes and thus probably the pigment content per biomass. It can be observed that the absorption peak at 680 nm tends to flatten as long as the cultivation time increases. This indicates a decrease in the concentration of chlorophyll a per biomass over the time course of cultivation. The peaks at 445 nm and 500 nm also tend to flatten, except that the absorbance increases between five and eight days and then continues to fall. Thus, it can also be assumed that the carotenoid content per biomass increases intermediately during the course of cultivation, but decreases overall.

The peak of chlorophyll b at 650 nm is clearly seen after three, five and eight days, but is no longer visible after 13 to 21 days. In summary, it can be inferred from the data presented that the pigment content per biomass decreases during the course of cultivation. This phenomenon has also been described for *C. vulgaris* in the literature and is enhanced by nitrogen deficiency [32].

In Figure 3.2 b), the spectrum of normalized absorbance referenced to 780 nm for *Flask B* generated by the same methods is shown and compared in the following with the spectrum of *Flask A* from Figure 3.2 a). In Figure 3.2 b), it can be seen that the chlorophyll a peaks at 445 nm and 680 nm, the chlorophyll b peak at 650 nm and the carotenoid peak at 500 nm decrease with increasing age of the culture, as is also the case for *Flask A*. However, unlike *Flask A*, no intermediate increase in absorbance is observed for *Flask B* between five and eight days at wavelengths below 650 nm. Furthermore, after 18 and 21 days, it can be seen that the normalized absorbance decreases toward lower wavelengths and is consistently below a value of one after 21 days. Since this decreasing behavior extends over the entire wavelength range, this effect probably cannot be explained by changing pigment concentrations alone. As the normalized absorbance falls below the value of one, it is clear that the fraction of absorbance in this wavelength range caused by scattering must be lower than at 780 nm. Griffith et al. also found that the scattering-induced absorbance is wavelength-dependent in bleached *C. vulgaris* cells. However, in the data presented there, the scatter-induced absorbance of bleached cells increases in the direction of smaller wavelengths and does not decrease as in experiment *Flask B* [32]. One possible explanation for the different relation between light scattering-dependent absorbance and wavelengths is that the morphology of the cells differs. However, to clarify this precisely, the methods presented in Chapter 2.3.2 would have to be used to directly determine the biomass and pigment concentration, as well as, for example, the cell morphology by microscopy or flow cytometry.

To support the motivation for multispectral analysis of microalgae, the growth curves of the two shake flask cultivations of *C. vulgaris*, *Flask A* and *Flask B*, are compared below. For this purpose, the absorbance of the two cultures measured at 780 nm is plotted versus time in Figure 3.3 and can be read from the right y-axis. As in the previous considerations, it is assumed that the course of absorbance at 780 nm is linear to the course of biomass concentration. At the beginning of the growth from the third to the fifth day, the absorbance at 780 nm of both cultures is overlapping, which indicates that the cultures grow at the same rate at the beginning. However,

Figure 3.2: Absorbance spectrum of diluted *C. vulgaris* samples at different cultivation times. The data from each day is normalized by the absorbance at 780 nm. The curves represent the mean over three samples of the respective flask. Cultivation conditions: $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, 100 rpm, and continuous light. a): cultivation *Flask A*, b): cultivation *Flask B*.

Figure 3.3: Comparison between biomass related absorbance and normalized pigment related absorbances along the *C. vulgaris* cultivations *Flask A* (solid lines, closed symbols) and *Flask B* (dashed lines, empty symbols). Absorbances at 500 nm (green squares) and 686 nm (red triangles) are normalized with the respective measuring point specific absorbance at 780 nm (left y-axis). Biomass related absorbance at 780 nm (right y-axis). Error bars indicate the standard deviation over three samples. Cultivation conditions: $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, 100 rpm, and continuous light.

with increasing cultivation time, a higher absorbance is measured for *Flask A* than for *Flask B*. At the end of cultivation after 21 days, the absorbance and thus the biomass concentration is approximately 20 % higher for *Flask A* than for *Flask B*. The different rates of microalgae growth are indicative of different physiological states of the cells. If only the absorbance at 780 nm is used to monitor the microalgae, one would conclude that the cultures have the same state at the beginning of cultivation because they grow at the same rate. And one could assume that only after about five days the states of *Flask B* deteriorate compared to *Flask A*, so from this point on *Flask B* grows slower.

However, the information on the absorbance spectra discussed previously in Figure 3.2

can be used to refute this hypothesis. For this purpose, Figure 3.3 additionally plots the normalized absorbance discussed in Figure 3.2 at the wavelengths of the previously identified pigment absorption maxima of the carotenoids lutein and β -carotene at 500 nm and chlorophyll a at 686 nm on the left y-axis. One can clearly see, as previously discussed, the decreasing normalized absorbance with increasing age of the culture. In addition, it can be seen that the normalized absorbance of all wavelengths considered here for *Flask B* is already significantly below the level of *Flask A* after three days and also decreases more sharply by the fifth day. This shows that the cell state of the two shake flask cultures does not begin to differ only gradually after the fifth day. Instead, a clear difference in cell state is also present by the third day, as indicated by a lower pigment content per biomass in culture *Blask B*. This finding motivates for the use of multispectral sensors for monitoring microalgae because they can provide early information about changing cell states.

3.2 Sensor development

The central theme of this work is the development of the multispectral optical sensor that can be integrated into the bypass of a photobioreactor. As presented in Chapter 2.3.2, there are already some approaches reported in literature for such a sensor. However, these remain imprecise in the information content for the design and geometries of the sensor and vary in implementation. Therefore, there is some flexibility and approaches that could be considered in the development of the sensor system for on-line monitoring of microalgae. First, the concept of the measurement is crucial, i.e. which optical properties of the microalgae should be investigated and how this should be implemented. For this purpose, it must be determined which wavelengths are to be used and at which angle the emerging light is to be measured. Then it must be decided how the flow-through cell should be constructed. Once these decisions are made, the sensor housing can be developed, which should fix the components and enable the planned light paths. This housing should be as flexible as possible to fit the dimensions of the light sources and photodiodes. Finally, in addition to the design of the sensor, measurement software must be developed to obtain a functional sensor. The results of these steps are shown in the following sections.

3.2.1 Measurement concept - light source and angle

The project in which this work is embedded aims to develop a software sensor system for the on-line monitoring of microalgae. The multispectral sensor developed in this work should provide versatile data, which can be used to estimate biological process parameters. Nevertheless, the target parameters of the sensor developed here must be limited. First, it should be possible to use the sensor data to obtain a measure of biomass concentration, which, as discussed in Chapter 2.3.2, is the basis for monitoring and is therefore very important for the evaluation of all other measurement data. In addition, the sensor should provide information about the pigment content. As presented in Chapter 2.3.2, this is not only relevant for the direct production of pigments, but also provides information about the physiological state of the culture. Potential indications of the informative value of pigment content per biomass on the progression of the growth curve were also shown in Chapter 3.1.2.

As presented in Chapter 2.3.2, scattered light measurement methods are suitable to determine the biomass concentration. Depending on the angle at which the scattered light is measured, one can adjust the measurement sensitivity to the prevailing conditions. As explained in Chapter 2.1.2, side scatter measurement is superior to backscatter measurement at low concentrations due to higher sensitivity. However, since at high concentrations the side scatter signal can drop again despite increasing biomass concentration, the backscatter measurement is also important. Therefore, both measurement principles should be enabled by the sensor. For this purpose, the side scatter is measured in a 90° angle by definition. The backscatter should be measured at as large angle as possible to maximize the additional information gain compared to the side scatter measurement. However, in practice, the measurement angle is limited by the space requirements of the light source and cannot be 180° . Murphy et al. approximate the biomass of a microalgal film by backscatter light measurement at a 160° angle [68]. Therefore, the sensor developed here is also intended to measure the backscattered light in 160° . In addition, biomass is also measured by attenuation in the transmission direction as part of turbidimetry. Thus, there are three measurands dependent on the biomass concentration. While these are all based on the principle of scattering, they measure it in different ways. By combining these measurements, data processing could make it possible to separate the effects of cell morphology and biomass concentration, which overlap in the scattered light measurement. Due to the changing pigment content per biomass, only light with a wavelength outside the

pigment absorption range can be considered for biomass determination. As shown in Figure 3.1, the wavelength must therefore be above about 710 nm. In this work, a wavelength of 780 nm is used for biomass determination [19].

To obtain information about the pigment absorption, the fluorescence or the transmission can be measured. However, since the fluorescence signal is weaker, this measurement method can no longer be used at higher attenuation [14]. In addition, the development effort is greater, since filters are needed to separate excitation light and fluorescence from each other. Therefore, in this work, transmittance is measured as in UV-Vis spectroscopy. Unlike in commercially available spectrophotometers, however, a nearly continuous spectrum cannot be generated, because this would significantly increase the development effort and cost. Instead, individual wavelengths must be selected whose absorption provides as much information as possible about the respective pigment concentration. Based on the results from Chapter 3.1, 500 nm offers a suitable measure for the absorption of carotenoids, in particular β -carotene and lutein [66]. However, chlorophyll b still absorbs some light at 500 nm. Therefore, as a compromise, 505 nm is chosen as the measuring light for lutein and β -carotene to allow a measurement independent of the chlorophyll content. Chlorophyll a has several absorption maxima, but they are most pronounced at 440 nm and around 680 nm as discussed in Figure 3.1 [66]. Therefore, due to the greater sensitivity to changes in chlorophyll a content, a wavelength in these ranges should be chosen. However, as shown in Figure 3.1, the absorption at 440 nm overlaps with that of chlorophyll b as well as carotenoids [65]. In order to obtain meaningful measurement signals for the chlorophyll a content, a wavelength in the range around 680 nm is therefore selected. However, as discussed in Chapter 3.1.1, the measured chlorophyll a peak of *C. vulgaris* is rather at 686 nm than at 680 nm and the absorption at 680 nm is still slightly influenced by the chlorophyll b concentration. Therefore, measuring light with 690 nm is chosen to realize an undisturbed measurement of the chlorophyll a content. As can be seen in Figure 3.1, the maximum absorption of chlorophyll b at 650 nm produces a peak in the measured absorbance spectrum. Therefore, light at 650 nm would be suitable for measuring a measure of chlorophyll b content. However, chlorophyll a also absorbs in this range and the peak in the absorbance spectrum is small compared to the chlorophyll a peaks and the carotenoid peak. Therefore, this work is limited to the estimation of the carotenoid and chlorophyll a content.

Once the measurement requirements have been defined, the light sources and photodetectors can be selected. As a light source for an optical sensor for monitoring

microalgae, laser diodes or LEDs are used in the literature as described in Chapter 2.3.2 [14, 19, 20]. Laser diodes have the advantage that their light offers a low spectral bandwidth [69]. In addition, they are available with higher light intensity outputs [70]. However, they are also more expensive, and emit light only when a certain operating current is exceeded [70]. Since the current source used provides a maximum current of 20 mA per output and this would further limit the choice of laser diodes, LEDs are used in this work. When selecting LEDs, care is taken to minimize the beam angle and the width of the emitted spectrum in order to better define and interpret the measurement results. Due to availability, 505 nm is used instead of 500 nm. Furthermore, LEDs with 780 nm and 690 nm are used as planned. The specifications of these LEDs can be found in Table 5.10 in the Appendix. To measure the light intensity photodiodes are used in dependence on their light sensitivity. A high light sensitivity makes it possible to measure small fluctuations in light intensity. However, a high sensitivity also leads to the limitation of the measuring range and high light intensities cannot be displayed. Initial experiments have shown that a less sensitive photodiode is required for the transmission measurement. Therefore, the OPT-photodiode is used for the transmission measurement. The intensity of the side scatter and backscatter is much lower, therefore the light sensitive SD-photodiodes are used to measure side scatter and backscatter. Comparison of the manufacturer's datasheets shows that the SD-photodiode is about 70 times more sensitive than the OPT-photodiode at 780 nm [71, 72].

The presented concept of the sensor in terms of measurement angles and light wavelengths is summarized in Figure 3.4.

3.2.2 Design of the flow-through cell

The next important point for sensor development is the technical implementation of a flow-through cell that will be integrated into the bypass of the photobioreactor. There are several options to choose from. For example, other previous studies on the development of on-line sensors in the field of biotechnology use glass tubes [20], modified disposable cuvettes [7, 19], commercial glass flow-through cells [19], or the combinations of 3D printing and glued quartz glass windows [73]. To keep the cost or development effort low, the realization by polished commercial glass flow-through cells and sensors with self-glued glass windows is not pursued further. And since the round

Figure 3.4: Schematic view of the measurement concept by means of an upper view on a cuvette filled with microalgae (gray circles). It shows the wavelength of the LEDs, the angular position, and target value of the photodiodes.

shape of a tube leads to more complex reflection behavior, the use of glass tubes is also avoided. Thus, the choice falls on rectangular disposable polystyrene cuvettes, which are also used in off-line UV-Vis spectrophotometers for measurements above the UV range. Polystyrene is a suitable material because it is transparent in the visible light range and at 780 nm [74].

Besides advantages such as the low purchase price and standardization, the use of disposable cuvettes also poses challenges. On the one hand, the disposable cuvettes are not designed as flow-through cells but as containers and are therefore open only on one side. One could run an inlet and an outlet tube through the same opening. This would require the inlet tube to reach the bottom of the cuvette to avoid a short-circuit flow. However, this tube would then partially block the light path. Therefore, the disposable cuvette is modified to a flow-through cell with two opposite openings.

The second challenge is the connection of the rectangular cuvette with the bypass. A silicone molding is identified as a functional bonding technique. The silicone is used to make plugs that seal both openings from the modified cuvette (see Appendix). Each

silicone plug has a hole through it. In every hole one connector tube is placed in order to join the modified cuvette with the bypass. Both connections show a hermetic seal. The flow-through cell is shown in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5: Self-built flow-through cell. a): 3D view of the flow-through cell, which consists of a standard polystyrene cuvette connected via silicone plugs to the bypass tubing. b): Side view of the flow-through cell with dimensions.

3.2.3 Design of the sensor housing

The sensor housing must provide several functionalities. First, it must fix the LEDs, the photodiodes and the flow-through cell. This must ensure that the components are always at the same distance and proper angle to each other for a given setup. It is also responsible for ensuring that the origin of the light, which reaches the photodiodes, is clearly defined. This includes the shielding of reflections inside the housing as well as shielding the photodiodes from ambient light that could enter the sensor housing from the outside. In addition, it should be possible to adapt the sensor housing as flexibly as possible to different designs of LEDs and photodiodes. Furthermore, the assembly and disassembly of the sensor housing should be as simple and fast as possible in order to save time when replacing parts. To meet these requirements, the sensor housing

is developed through iterative rapid prototyping using 3D printing, as described in the methodology section. The design avoids the use of screw connections due to the soft 3D printing material polylactide acid (PLA). Instead, plug-in connections are used, which are sufficient due to the low mechanical stress.

In the following, the three basic elements of the sensor housing are presented first, which fix the flow-through cell and provide slots for further adapters. These consist of a bottom part, a tension cap and a top cap. The appearance of these parts and their relative position to each other can be seen in Figure 3.6. For a better overview, the adapters are not shown there. The bottom part embeds the flow-through cell and provides the two slots for the adapters to measure the side scatter and the transmission. After the flow-through cell is placed, the two still open sides are closed by the tension cap and the top cap. The top cap also fixes the flow-through cell in place and provides the slot for the adapter that arranges the light sources and enables the backscatter measurement. In addition to shielding ambient light, the tension cap has the task of applying pressure to the silicone plugs via a plunger. The silicone plugs are thus pressed into the cuvette and seal it. A detailed illustration of the tension cap with plunger is shown in Figure 3.7. In addition, Figure 3.7 shows the bead. The bead is pressed as a clamping element into the joint of the top cap and the bottom part when the sensor is assembled. Furthermore, Figure 3.7 shows an example of cutouts. These are inserted in the tension cap and the top cap to make it easier to remove the clamping when disassembling the sensor housing.

Now that the basic structure of the sensor housing has been shown, the anchoring of the electronic components via the adapters will be discussed. The assembled sensor with adapters, LEDs and photodiodes is shown in Figure 3.8. There, the 3D-printed parts, which are matte black in reality, are shown in different colors so that they can be better distinguished from each other. Since important geometries that determine the light path are located inside the sensor housing, two sectional views are also used in the following. The orientation of the sectional views can be taken from the top view 3.8 b). The frontal section view is marked as C in the top view 3.8 b) and shown in Figure 3.8 c). The side section view is marked as D in the top view 3.8 b) and is shown in Figure 3.8 d).

Figure 3.6: Basic structure of the sensor housing. The flow-through cell lies in the cavity of the lower part of the sensor housing and is additionally fixed by the top cap and the tension cap. The opening for the slot of the transmission photodiode in the lower part is hidden in this view.

Adapters for photodiodes

First the SD-photodiode adapter and then the OPT-photodiode adapter are discussed. The SD-photodiodes used for side scatter and backscatter measurement have a cylindrical shape. Therefore, the adapters are used to connect the SD-photodiodes to the housing. They can be seen in Figure 3.8 a) and c). These adapters have a cylindrical recess into which the SD-photodiodes can be inserted with a precise fit. As can also be seen in the sectional view 3.8 c) the OPT-photodiode does not have a simple cylindrical shape. Therefore, a different type of adapter is used for it, which fixes the board of the OPT-photodiode via hooks. The adapter for the OPT-photodiode is shown in Figure 3.9 to explain its function.

As shown in 3.9 a), the adapter provides a support surface for the circuit board of the OPT-photodiode. When the circuit board rests on this surface, the OPT-photodiode protrudes through the opening provided for it and can be used to measure transmission. To prevent the photodiode and circuit board from moving, the circuit board is secured

Figure 3.7: Tension cap design. All dimensions are shown in millimeters.

with hooks. As can be seen in the magnification in Figure 3.9 a), these hooks protrude about 0.3 mm beyond the embedding of the circuit board, preventing it from shifting upward. To insert or remove the OPT-photodiode together with the circuit board from the adapter, the flexibility of the adapter is used. As shown in 3.9 b), a force is applied to the flanks of the adapter manually using both hands so that the adapter bends. As shown schematically in the enlargement, this causes the hooks to protrude less over the circuit board support surface so that the circuit board can be inserted or removed. Furthermore, a cap is used which is placed over the circuit board and the hooks. This is necessary to shield further ambient light from the interior of the sensor housing since the circuit board is transparent to light. Neither the cap nor the photodiode with the circuit board are shown in 3.9.

Adapter for LED placement and orientation of the backscatter measurement

As shown in Figure 3.8, the LEDs are housed in an attachment that is inserted into the opening of the top cap. In addition to placing the LEDs, the adapter is also needed to provide a light path for backscatter measurement and to position the SD-photodiode at the correct angle.

The LEDs are connected to their cables (not shown) via rectangular sockets. In the

Figure 3.8: a): Complete sensor assembly (LEDs, photodiodes, and adapters) for monitoring of microalgae cultivation. b): Upper view of the sensor to illustrate the position and viewing direction of section views C and D. c): Frontal section view C with side scatter and backscatter angles θ_{SS} and θ_{BS} dependent on distance X. d): Side section view D with the necessary emission angles of the side LEDs. All length dimensions are displayed in millimeters.

Figure 3.9: OPT-photodiode adapter. a): Normal state of the adapter. b): Indication where the forces (F) have to be applied to bend the adapter for placing or removing the circuit board with the photodiode. The circuit board and the photodiode are not shown.

sectional view 3.8 d) it can be seen that these sockets are inserted into an opening intended for them and the LEDs are fixed in this way in a row, parallel to each other. Each LED thus projects into a short tunnel through which the light falls onto the cuvette. The 780 nm LED is placed in the center. The manufacturer specifies a beam angle of 18° for the 780 nm LED. This means that at an angle of 9° to the LED axis, 50% of the maximum light intensity is still emitted. This can lead to reflections on the cuvette surface, which could superimpose the measurement of the backscattered light. Therefore, a conical aperture is added behind the short tunnel of the 780 nm LED. It has a diameter of 1.9 mm at the exit. A smaller diameter is not possible due to the lack of reproducibility of the printing process. As shown in the enlarged sectional view 3.8 d), this retains LED radiation that deviates more than 7° from the LED axis. However, this statement can only be made if one assumes a point light source at the LED tip and neglects reflections at the cone surface. As one can see in the side view 3.8 d) the transmission or the absorbance of all three LEDs is measured with only one OPT-photodiode. Multiple OPT-photodiodes were not used side by side for space reasons because the OPT-photodiode adapter is relatively large. Instead, the radiation angle of the LEDs arranged on the side is used. As shown in the side section view of the sensor 3.8 d), only light emitted at about an angle of 8.5° to the axis of

the lateral LEDs can reach the measuring surface of the OPT-photodiode unhindered. This angle increases the direct light path length through the suspension by about 1% from 10 mm to 10.1 mm. As presented in Equation 2.4 in Chapter 2.1, the absorbance is linear to the light path length through the suspension in the range of validity of the Lambert-Beer law. Therefore, one can expect that the extended light path for the lateral LEDs results in 1% higher absorbance than if it was measured at the 0° angle. In addition to placing the LEDs, the adapter is also needed to define a light path for the backscatter measurement and to position the SD-photodiode together with its adapter. The geometrical arrangement of this light path can be seen in the sectional view in Figure 3.8 c).

Resulting measurement angles

As described before in Figure 3.4 the back scatter signal is planned to be measured in 160° and the side scatter signal in 90° . By definition, transmission should be measured in 0° . However, these exact angles would only be possible if the light channels have a very small diameter. Because only then the origin of the light can be limited to one point in the cuvette. This would strongly reduce the measurable light intensity and thus increase the negative influence of noise. Therefore, larger channels were used in this prototype. As shown in the sectional view 3.8 c), the diameter of the light channel leading to the transmission measurement is 6.3 mm, the light channel leading to the side scatter measurement is 8.3 mm and the narrowest point of the channel leading to backscatter measurement is 4.5 mm. For transmission measurement, this in combination with the beam angle of 7° leads to the fact that not only attenuation is measured but also the forward scattered light. With increasing particle concentration, this results in two opposing effects, since forward scattering of the widened light beam increases the measured transmission intensity and attenuation decreases it. However, it can probably be assumed that the intensity of forward scattered light is much lower compared to the intensity of unattenuated transmission. Nevertheless, this consideration should be included in the analysis of the measured transmission intensity. Also, for side scatter and backscatter measurements, the larger channels result in a widening of the measurement angle range. This is because even if one assumes that the LED ideally emits light only in the emission angle of 0° , the penetration depth of the light up to the point where the light is scattered differs. This results in the measured scattered light with one photodiode being a composition of light scattered at different

angles. In the frontal sectional view 3.8 c) this variable penetration depth is marked with the symbol X and drawn as an example for a penetration depth up to scattering of 5 mm. The angles of side scatter θ_{SS} and backscatter θ_{BS} in this case are 90° and 162° , respectively. However, if the scattering takes place immediately after entering the suspension ($X = 0\text{ mm}$) or just before leaving the suspension ($X = 10\text{ mm}$), the scattering angles for the side scattering light measurement θ_{SS} and backscattering light measurement θ_{BS} are 78° and 160° and 112° and 164° , respectively.

3.2.4 Design of measurement software

In order to operate the sensor, measurement software is developed in the Python programming language. This software controls the timing of the measurement and controls the current source of the LEDs and receives measurement data from the photodiodes via a microcontroller. In addition, the measurement data is stored in CSV files.

The core task of the measurement software is the control of the LEDs. As shown in the side view 3.8 d) the transmission of the light emitted by all three LEDs is measured with the same photodiode. In order to still be able to assign the measured values to a specific wavelength, only one LED may emit light at a time. In addition, the stored data must contain the information which LED is switched on at the time of measurement. To make this possible, a sequential structure of the software is chosen, in which modular functions are called. For an overview, the flow of the program is shown schematically as a flow-chart diagram in Figure 3.10.

There you can see that the program first runs through the initialization after the start. During the initialization the parameters entered by the user before the start of the program are read out. Depending on the application purpose, the parameters can be assigned to the measurement setup, the sequential order or temporal organization. The parameters concerning the measurement setup include the assignment of the photodiode and LED positions to the connections of the microcontroller or the current source. It is also possible to activate a simulation mode that can be used for software development without a power source or microcontroller. The parameters concerning the sequence or measuring sequence define the configuration of individual measuring points and their frequency. The core element for this is a list containing the different measurement configurations. A measurement configuration is called mode in the fol-

Figure 3.10: Flow chart diagram of the developed software for measurements with the new sensor.

lowing. One LED and one measuring angle are defined per mode. To achieve a suitable measuring range depending on LED and measuring angle, an operating current of the selected LED is also defined for the respective mode. Furthermore, the parameter n_B defines how many measuring points are to be measured per mode. The remaining parameters can be assigned to the temporal organization of the measurement. Thereby the parameter t_m defines how long should be waited between the repetitions of the single measuring points of a mode and the parameter t_c how long the waiting time between single measuring cycles. A measuring cycle contains the measurement of all modes with their number of repetitions n_B .

After initialization, the program enters three loops, layered in each other. The inner-

most loop is shown in yellow in Figure 3.10. With the settings of the current mode, n_B measurement points are collected in this loop with a time offset of t_m seconds. Each measurement point contains the actual time and the signals of all photodiodes. After that, the innermost loop is exited and the program continues to run at the level of the middle loop, shown in green in Figure 3.10. This middle loop goes through all the modes defined in the initialization by controlling the current levels applied to the LEDs. For each new mode set, the program re-enters the innermost loop. A measurement cycle is completed when the middle loop has been run through for all modes. Then the middle loop is left and the program continues in the outermost loop, which is shown in blue in Figure 3.10. Here all LEDs are switched off. In this loop, first, all CSV files and the graphical visualization of the running experiment are updated with the measurement data of the just finished measurement cycle. On the one hand, all n_b measuring points of each mode are written into a CSV file. In addition, in order to simplify the analysis of the data, the measurement of each mode is averaged over the n_B measurement points and stored in further CSV files specific to the particular measurement angle. After the save operation, the outermost loop checks to see if a stop command was entered via the console during the last measurement cycle. If this is the case, the program stops until the command to continue the measurement is entered. This function makes it possible to make modifications to the sensor during the experiment without saving false data during this time. After that, the program goes into a waiting state for t_c seconds. For slowly changing sample properties, this waiting time is useful to avoid an overflow of data and to reduce the time span in which the sample is illuminated by the LEDs. When measuring microalgae, the shortened illumination time is intended to reduce the risk of biofilm formation within the cuvette. After the waiting time has elapsed, the LED of the first mode is switched on. Then the program re-enters the two inner loops and starts the next measurement cycle. This circulation is only interrupted when the program within the innermost loop determines that a stop criterion has been met. This is the case when the maximum duration of the experiment is exceeded or the maximum number of measuring cycles has been reached.

3.3 Sensor evaluation with chemicals

After the concept for the sensor has been developed and it has been implemented through 3D printing and software development into a system that can be used in prac-

tice, the validity of the sensor's measurement data must be tested. Since microalgae represent a complex system and it is difficult to accurately determine and standardize the condition of microalgae, chemicals are used for preliminary validation of the developed sensor in off-line operation.

3.3.1 Evaluation with ink

Water-soluble ink for fountain pens contains dissolved dyes and is therefore suitable for testing the absorption measurement of the sensor. Assuming that fountain pen ink does not contain particles, no scattering caused by particles is to be expected, which would overlay the pure absorption. The goal is to find out if the absorbance measured by the sensor is quantitatively comparable to the absorbance measured by a reference spectrophotometer. To this purpose, the reference spectrum recorded by the off-line spectrophotometer for different dilutions of the ink is first discussed. The recorded reference spectrum is shown in Figure 3.11.

The letters on the curves in Figure 3.11 describe the concentration of the samples. c_{max} is the sample with the highest concentration. The other curves marked with p to w represent samples with lower concentrations in alphabetic decreasing order. The exact dilution values can be taken from Table 5.1 in the Appendix. In Figure 3.11 one can clearly see the absorption maxima at about 590 nm and as expected the absorbance increases with the ink concentration. An exception is the plateau of the curve with maximum concentration c_{max} . This is below the curve of concentration of sample p . This inconsistency and the existence of the plateau show that the spectrophotometer can no longer resolve accurately the signal above an absorbance of a value of 2.2. Therefore, only the measured values of samples q to w are used as references in the following. The absorbance at wavelengths above 800 nm is about zero for all concentrations. This confirms the assumption that scattering plays a negligible role in the measurement of ink and clearly distinguishes the spectrum of ink from that of the microalgae suspensions from Chapter 3.1.

To test the newly developed sensor with ink, a suitable wavelength is selected. Since 505 nm and 690 nm are relatively far from the peak at 590 nm, a LED with 625 nm is used. The result of the sensor measurement is shown in Figure 3.12. There, the transmission and side scatter signals are plotted on the left y-axis versus the ink concentration of the sample, which is referenced to c_{max} . In order to be able to compare

Figure 3.11: Wavelength scan of ink measured with the reference spectrophotometer at different dilutions indicated by letters. c_{max} : highest measured concentration, $p - w$: concentrations decreasing in alphabetical order. The explicit concentrations are shown in Table 5.1 (Appendix). Intersections of curves with the vertical red dashed line indicate the respective absorbances at 625 nm. Measurements were performed in triplicates.

the transmission signal with the side scatter signal, they are normalized to the respective measurement signal of pure water which is the blank value. This is for the transmission signal, as shown in Chapter 2.1.1 in equation 2.2, the relative transmittance T' . Both the normalized transmittance and the normalized side scatter signal decrease approximately exponentially with increasing ink concentration. While this trend in transmittance is also to be expected for cell suspensions, the side scatter signal shows a special feature that needs to be addressed in more detail. This is because, although ink is a homogeneous liquid, a side scatter signal is measurable, especially at low concentrations. Molecules also scatter light [28]. But it is questionable whether this is sufficient to explain the effect, since scattering at particles much smaller than the wavelength of light is low [29]. Another possible explanation is that the measured scattered light is due to the non-ideality of the sensor. The LED used emits light at an angle of 30° and no aperture behind the LED as presented in Chapter 3.2.3 was used in this experiment. As a result, light may be reflected off the cuvette or housing in such a way that it reaches the side-mounted photodiode. The decrease in this scattered light with increasing ink concentration can be explained by the fact that the reflected or scattered light must pass through the ink before it falls on the side-mounted photodiode and attenuation by absorption occurs in the same way as in the transmission direction. In addition, it can be seen in Figure 3.12 that the relative side scatter signal falls faster at low concentrations and thus reacts more sensitively to an increase in concentration than the relative transmittance. A possible explanation for this is that the measured side scatter signal is the sum of many different reflections through the sample and these light paths are on average longer than the path of the transmitting light through the sample.

To validate the transmission signal measured with the sensor and to compare the sensor measurement with the reference spectrophotometer, the absorbance value is required. This is calculated from the relative transmittance as described in Equation 2.4 from Chapter 2.1.1 and is plotted on the right y-axis in Figure 3.12 and displayed as empty circles. According to the Lambert-Beer model from Equation 2.4, a linear relationship between ink concentration and absorbance is expected. This is verified in Figure 3.12 by a linear regression of the calculated absorbance. The linear regression is applied to those measurement points marked with black empty circles and the result is shown as a blue dashed line. The relationship between concentration and absorbance can be approximated very well by a straight line up to an absorbance of about 1.8 ($r^2 = 0.997$). Measuring points whose absorbance lies outside this linear range are shown in Figure 3.12 as light gray empty circles and were not included in the regression. It can be seen

Figure 3.12: Investigation of the side scatter and transmission signal of the newly developed sensor using ink at varying concentrations at 625 nm. Side scatter (red triangles) and transmission signal (filled black cycles) are normalized to its respective mean blank value and plotted on the left y-axis. The absorbance (empty black and gray cycles) calculated from the shown transmission data is plotted on the right y-axis. The linear regression (dashed blue line) applied to the absorbance measurement points represented by black empty circles has a coefficient of determination of $r^2 = 0.997$. The standard deviation of the triplicate measurements is indicated by error bars.

that the absorbance curve flattens towards high concentrations. This is probably due, as explained in Chapter 2.1.1, to the range of validity of the Lambert-Beer law being limited to low and moderate concentrations.

To check the validity of the sensor data, the absorbance calculated from the sensor transmission signal is compared with the absorbance from the reference spectrophotometer measurement. For this purpose, only the measured values at 625 nm are extracted from the absorbance spectra of the reference spectrophotometer shown in Figure 3.11. In Figure 3.11 these are the intersections of the spectra with the red dashed vertical line. The comparison of the measured values is discussed in Figure 3.13. There, the absorbance measured with the reference spectrophotometer at 625 nm is plotted versus the absorbance calculated from the transmission signal of the sensor measurement. A clear linear relationship can be seen. This is checked by a linear regression. The result is shown in Figure 3.13 as a blue dashed straight line and its calculated coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.999$) shows an explicit linear relationship. This proves that the sensor measurement for ink up to an absorbance of 1.8 provides very similar information as the measurement with the reference spectrophotometer. Furthermore, the slope of the regression line of 1.065 shows that the measurement data of the two instruments are almost identical and that the spectrophotometer measures an absorbance only 6.5% higher than the sensor. This discrepancy can be explained by the non-idealities of the measuring instruments. Jia et al. suggested that the reason for the deviation is that the LED used does not emit monochromatic light but a limited spectrum. The manufacturer states that the spectrum of the 625 nm LED used for the ink experiment emits light over a range of 20 nm with at least half of its maximum light intensity [70]. Since, as shown in Figure 3.11, the absorption of ink at 625 nm does not occur at the absorption peak but in a flank of the absorption spectrum and the absorption at 625 nm thus depends strongly on the wavelength even in the near vicinity 625 nm, the explanatory approach is also reasonable for this experiment. Furthermore, the standard deviation calculated over three measurements of the same sample is shown in Figure 3.13 by horizontal error bars for the spectrophotometer measurement and by vertical error bars for the sensor measurement. This shows that the standard deviation, and thus the precision of the absorbance measurement with the sensor, is at the same level as that of the reference spectrophotometer. Finally, for the comparison between spectrophotometer and sensor, it should be mentioned that the maximum measurable concentration of ink with the sensor is significantly higher than the maximum measurable concentration with the spectrophotometer. As already discussed in the Figures 3.11 and 3.12, in contrast to the sensor, with the spectropho-

tometer it is not possible to measure the higher concentrated sampled p and c_{max} . This results in a at least twice as high maximal measurable ink concentration with the sensor compared to the spectrophotometer.

Figure 3.13: Comparison between off-line spectrophotometric measurements and the off-line optical flow-through cell sensor measurements of ink absorbance at 625 nm. The linear regression (dashed blue line) has a slope of $m = 1.065$ and a coefficient of determination of $r^2 = 0.999$. The standard deviation of the triplicate measurements is indicated by error bars.

Through the previous discussion, it can be summarized that the transmission measurement signal of the sensor is valid and provides similar accuracy and precision as the measurement of the spectrophotometer using a single wavelength when measuring ink. Thus, the sensor can be used to study the absorption behavior of homogeneous samples and to estimate their concentration.

3.3.2 Evaluation with formazin

In the on-line monitoring of microalgae, a suspension of cells and not a homogeneous solution as in the case of the previously treated ink is measured. Therefore, it is useful to evaluate the sensor function by a model system that contains particles, as the microalgae suspension does. For this purpose, the polymer suspension formazin presented in Chapter 2.1.2, which usually serves as a calibration standard for turbidity measurements, is used for sensor evaluation by off-line operation. For this, a sensor assembly as presented in Figure 3.8 in Chapter 3.2.3 is used with the lateral 505 nm 690 nm LEDs as well as the central 780 nm LED. The measured relation between the formazin concentration, the side scatter and the absorbance, is shown in Figure 3.14 for all three wavelengths. The side scatter signal is plotted on the left y-axis, which is represented by full symbols in the diagram. The signal is normalized by dividing with the blank value to compare the data from the different LEDs. It can be seen that the side scatter signal for all three wavelengths increases with increasing formazin concentration. This is already a significant difference from the optical behavior of ink discussed in Chapter 3.3.1. With the operating currents of the LEDs used, the increase in the side scatter can be measured up to 200 NTU or up to 260 NTU. At higher concentrations, the scattering is so intense that the intensity of the light falling on the side scatter photodiode is out of the measurement range. In Figure 3.14 it can be seen that due to the normalization of the side scatter signal, the curves of all three LEDs are very close to each other. The measurement at 505 nm leads to a slightly steeper increase in relative scattered light intensity while the measurement signal at 780 nm and 690 nm is slightly flatter and almost identical. In Figure 3.14, on the right y-axis, the absorbance calculated from the relative transmittance according to the formula 2.4 is plotted and represented by empty symbols in the diagram. The absorbance also increases with increasing formazin concentration for each LED used. In this case, the absorbance measured with 505 nm increases twice as steeply as with 690 nm or 780 nm. It is also observed in the literature that shorter wavelengths are more strongly scattered by formazin because the wavelength is of the same order of magnitude as some formazin particles [75]. However, as addressed earlier, this effect is not clearly visible in the case of side scattering. To investigate whether the relationship between side scattering or absorbance and formazin concentration is linear, a linear regression is performed for each of the three LEDs. The regressions are shown as dashed lines in Figure 3.14 and each of these linear regressions has a coefficient of determination of $r^2 > 0.999$. This shows that for formazin, at least up to a concentration of

Figure 3.14: Side scatter and absorbance measured with the newly developed sensor at different formazin concentrations. The side scatter signals (closed symbols) are normalized with the respective mean blank value and plotted on the left y-axis. Absorbance is plotted on the right y-axis. The measurements were performed with 505 nm (green squares), 690 nm (red triangles) and 780 nm (black circles). The standard deviation of the triplicates is indicated by error bars. Each linear regression (dashed lines) has $r^2 > 0.999$.

400 NTU, the absorbance is linear with respect to the concentration and thus the Lambert-Beer law is valid in this concentration range, although it is a suspension and not a homogeneous solution. Furthermore, it is shown that linearity also holds for the side scatter signal for formazin concentrations up to at least 200 NTU and 260 NTU, respectively. This result is particularly important for the 780 nm LED, since it will be used to measure the turbidity of microalgal suspensions both nephelometrically and turbidimetrically in order to draw conclusions about the biomass concentration as described in Chapter 3.2.1.

In addition to measuring the side scatter and the transmitted light, the developed

sensor, as shown before in Chapter 3.2.3, also allows the measurement of the intensity of the light backscattered in 160° . This signal is measured simultaneously with the side and transmission signal. The recorded backscatter signal for the three LEDs used is plotted in Figure 3.15 over the formazin concentrations as discussed before. In order to be able to compare backscatter signal of the different LEDs with each other, the shown measurement signal is again normalized by the respective mean blank backscatter signal of pure water. And to better understand the course, the measurement points are interpolated with straight lines.

Figure 3.15: Backscatter signal of the newly developed sensor at different formazin concentrations measured with 505 nm (green squares), 690 nm (red triangles) and 780 nm (black cycles). The signal is normalized to its respective mean blank value. The standard deviation of the triplicates is indicated by error bars.

It can be seen in Figure 3.15 that the backscatter signal for all three LEDs drops off abruptly between 0 NTU to 2 NTU. Thereafter, it increases roughly linearly up to a formazin concentration of 40 NTU until it is at a level similar to that of pure water. As the formazin concentration increases further, the measurement signals from the

different LEDs increasingly diverge from each other. The backscatter signal of the laterally arranged 505 nm LED is shown with green squares and reaches a maximum at a formazin concentration of 100 NTU, which is at the level of the blank. After that, the backscatter signal decreases to the highest investigated concentration of 400 NTU. There, the measured value of the 505 nm LED lies again on the level as at a formazin concentration of 2 NTU. The backscatter signal of the 690 nm LED increases up to a formazin concentration of 200 NTU to a value about 6% higher than the backscatter signal with pure water. There the signal reaches a plateau and remains relatively constant from 200 to 400 NTU. The measurement signal from the centrally positioned 780 nm LED has a similar curve to that of the 690 nm LED. However, it reaches a higher level at 200 NTU, which is about 20% above the signal of the blank. From these observations, it can be concluded that with the sensor used, it is much more difficult to infer the formazin concentration from the backscatter measurement than with the side scatter measurement and the absorbance measurement. This is shown by the fact that no larger range with a linear relationship to the formazin concentration can be found for all three LEDs in the backscatter measurement. This disadvantage can be compensated by a non-linear calibration curve. However, it is problematic that the backscatter signal does not increase strictly monotonously but can reach a plateau or maximum as shown. As a result, it is not always possible to find a unique relationship between the measurement signal and the concentration. Moreover, the relative increase of the backscatter signal at 200 NTU by a factor of 1.2 related to the blank value of pure water is very small. In comparison, as shown in Figure 3.14, the relative side scatter signal in the same concentration range already increased by a factor of 12. Thus, the side scatter signal for formazin in the concentration range considered is 10 times more sensitive to changes in the formazin concentration than the backscatter signal. This is partly due to the level of disturbing light intensity, which is already measurable in pure water.

This measured disturbing light intensity I_{blank} is not scattered by particles in the sample because the water is homogeneous. As in the experiment with ink in Chapter 3.3.1, the disturbing light probably reaches the respective photodiode instead by reflections from other surfaces. Table 3.1 compares this measured disturbing intensity for all three LEDs. Since different current intensities are used for the different modes and, according to the manufacturer, the intensity of the light emitted by the LED is proportional to the current intensity, the measured signal I_{blank} is divided by the respective current intensity to obtain the normalized intensity $I_{blank,norm}$ [70]. For each LED, the quotient of the normalized intensity of the backscatter measurement and the side scatter measurement

is then displayed in the last row of Table 3.1. This shows that for the 505 nm LED and the 690 nm LED, 20 times more of the reflected disturbing light is measured from the backscatter photodiode than from the side scatter photodiode. For the centrally positioned 780 nm LED provided with aperture, this quotient is even as high as 30.

Table 3.1: Comparison of the intensity of the disturbing light measured with side scatter photodiode (side) and the backscatter photodiode (back) using pure water (blank). Therefore, the signals are normalized to the respectively used operating current of the LEDs.

LED	unit	505 nm		690 nm		780 nm	
scatter direction		side	back	side	back	side	back
blank intensity I_{blank}	[-]	3015	5295	3067	5366	2433	5582
operating current	[mA]	1.7	0.15	4	0.35	20	1.5
$I_{blank,norm}$	[1/mA]	1774	35300	767	15331	122	3721
$\frac{I_{blank,norm,back}}{I_{blank,norm,side}}$	[-]	19.9		20		30.6	

In summary, the optical investigation of formazin with the newly developed sensor shows that both absorbance and side scatter measurement are very suitable for determining the formazin concentration up to at least 260 and 400 NTU, respectively. Due to the high noise level caused by disturbing light, the backscatter measurement is less suitable because it is less sensitive to concentration changes and does not increase monotonously with the formazin concentration. These are important insights for the development of the sensor and indicate that turbidity measurement in the 90° direction and in the 0° direction with the 780 nm LED can also be used to infer the biomass concentration of the microalgae suspension. However, it must be noted that formazin particles differ significantly from microalgae in their scattering properties. Most formazin particles have a diameter between $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ and are therefore smaller than, for example, the microalga *C. vulgaris* whose cell diameter is $2 \mu\text{m}$ to $10 \mu\text{m}$ [5, 76]. Furthermore, the structure of microalgae consisting of the membrane and internal components is much more complex, which also leads to different scattering behavior. This is also reflected in the fact that the refractive index of microalgae affecting the scattering is about 1.36 while it is about 1.57 for formazin particles [38, 77]. In addition to the different optical properties, it must also be noted when interpreting the data that the maximum turbidity studied for formazin is relatively low, with an absorbance around 0.5. Indeed, cultivations of *C. vulgaris* achieve an undiluted absorbance of more than 2 in the shake flask cultivations performed or in the photobioreactor (data not shown).

3.4 Sensor evaluation with *C. vulgaris* in the bypass of a photobioreactor

In the previous chapter, it was demonstrated in an off-line operation using ink and formazin that the newly developed sensor is suitable for determining the concentration of colored solutions and suspensions. This indicates that the sensor can also be used to approximate the biomass concentration and pigment concentration of microalgae. However, as explained in the previous section 3.3.2, the measurement result of formazin cannot be directly transferred to microalgae. Therefore, it is very important to test the sensor function on living microalgae. The aim of this work is the development of an on-line flow-through cell sensor for monitoring microalgae, which can be integrated into the bypass of a photobioreactor. Up to this point, only off-line experiments have been performed, with a measurement time spanning a short period of a few minutes. Therefore, it is very important to find out how the measurement signals of the sensor behave during continuous flow of a suspension of growing microalgae in the bypass of a photobioreactor. To check this, two *C. vulgaris* cultivations in the photobioreactor, the setup of which can be taken from the Appendix, are described in the following. In order to distinguish between the two cultivations, the first cultivation lasting 17 days is called *PBR1* and the second cultivation lasting 21 days is called *PBR2*. In order to draw conclusions about the functionality of the sensor, both cultivations are monitored by the newly developed sensor as well as by off-line samples. The parameters of the newly developed measurement software for the sensor, presented in Chapter 3.2.4, are adapted to these long-term experiments. Thereby, the sensor measures in each measurement mode every five minutes by averaging over five individual measurement points.

3.4.1 On-line approximation of biomass concentration

In the following, it will be first discussed whether the on-line flow-through sensor is suitable to determine the biomass concentration of microalgae in the bypass of a photobioreactor. For this purpose, the measured values at 780 nm are discussed, which, as discussed in Chapter 3.1, are not affected by fluctuating pigment concentrations and are therefore suitable for estimating the biomass concentration [32]. The measured data at 780 nm are shown for the *PBR1* cultivation in Figure 3.16. To be able to

display them on one axis, the respective measured value is normalized by its maximum value within the measurement period.

Figure 3.16: Monitoring of the growth of the *C. vulgaris* cultivation *PBR1* in a photobioreactor by different signals normalized to their maximum. Signals measured with the newly developed on-line sensor in the bypass of the photobioreactor with the 780 nm LED mounted on central position are shown as lines. Absorbance measured by off-line spectrophotometry at 780 nm via dilution is shown by black circles with error bars indicating the standard deviation over three samples. Cultivation conditions: 23 °C and continuous light.

Due to the dilution of the off-line samples, the Lambert-Beer law is valid and therefore the absorbance measured with the spectrophotometer is linearly proportional to the biomass concentration in the photobioreactor after multiplication by the dilution factor. This is true as long as the optical properties of the individual microalgae remain the same during cultivation. It is assumed that this is the case. Therefore, in the following, as in Chapter 3.1, the absorbance measured off-line with the spectrophotometer is considered as a measure of the biomass concentration and is referred to as the reference absorbance. The reference absorbance of the off-line samples measured with the spectrophotometer averaged over three samples is shown by black circles in

Figure 3.16. It can be seen that the reference absorbance increases very slowly within the first three days and then increases maximally toward the fourth day. From the fourth to the seventeenth day, the reference absorbance increases approximately linearly, with a brief stagnation observed between the fifth and sixth day. Furthermore, in Figure 3.16 the standard deviation of the reference absorbance determined over three samples is shown by black horizontal error bars. The standard deviation is relatively low towards the fourth day and assumes higher values from the fourth day onwards. This can be explained by the fact that at higher biomass concentrations higher dilutions are needed for the off-line measurement and thus the dilution error increases.

Furthermore, Figure 3.16 shows the absorbance (black dashed line), which is calculated from the transmission signal, the side scatter signal (solid red line) and the backscatter signal (green dash-dotted line) of the sensor. The opacity is also plotted, which is the inverse of the relative transmittance T' (blue dotted line). It has been reported in the literature that opacity is suitable for monitoring yeast and animal cells [73]. Therefore, it is of interest to investigate this for microalgae as well. In Figure 3.16 it can be seen that the absorbance, the side scatter signal and the opacity measured by the sensor follow the reference absorbance and thus the biomass concentration and allow a stable monitoring over the measurement period of 17 days. Interestingly, both the side scatter measurement and the two measurements based on the transmission signal, the opacity and the absorbance, show a possible stagnation of growth between five and six days, which is indicated by a bend in the curves. This is an indication that the bend between five and six days, which is also measured with the reference spectrophotometer, is indeed due to an intermediate slowdown in the growth of the microalgae. Without the on-line measurement using the sensor, this stagnation might not have been noticed, as it might have been interpreted as a measurement error of the spectrophotometer. Interestingly, the same stage is also observed in the measured values of the cultivation *PBR2* (not shown). Furthermore, it can be seen in Figure 3.16 that the absorbance of the sensor is more sensitive to the growth of microalgae at low concentrations than at high concentrations. This biomass concentration dependent sensitivity can be explained by deviations from the Lambert-Beer law at higher concentrations. The course of the backscatter signal shown as a green dash-dotted line in Figure 3.16 differs significantly from the courses of the three previously discussed sensor signals. This is because the backscatter signal does not increase monotonically, but drops drastically after an initial rising phase between the third and the fifth day. From the fifth day on, the signal remains relatively constant with a slight slope. Therefore, on-line backscatter measurement in monitoring microalgae with the newly developed sensor setup does

not provide easily interpretable results. This was already indicated by the evaluation with formazin in Chapter 3.3.2. A decreasing backscatter signal at the beginning of cultivation has also been reported in the literature when monitoring a yeast [73]. There it has been shown that the backscatter signal is only suitable for monitoring yeast growth at high turbidity levels [73]. The slight but continuous slope of the backscatter signal from the fifth day onwards observed in Figure 3.16 suggests that the backscatter signal could also be used in monitoring microalgae at higher cell densities. However, since the backscatter signal is much less sensitive than the other signals discussed in the concentration range considered, it will not be investigated further below.

At this point, a very important finding can already be formulated. Namely, the measurement signals of the optical multi-wavelength sensor previously discussed in Figure 3.16 show a stable measurement over more than two weeks. This is possible among other reasons because the flow-through cell is watertight during cultivation. This is an important result because it shows that the sealing of the flow-through cell presented in Chapter 3.2.2 performs its function over a longer period of time and despite slight overpressure. Furthermore, *C. vulgaris* does not form a visible biofilm on the cell surface (observation not shown). Whether this is also true for other microalgae species cannot be clarified at this point.

One application goal is to determine the biomass concentration using the measured data of the sensor. It is assumed that the same linear relationship exists between the reference absorbance measured off-line with the spectrophotometer and the biomass concentration over the entire cultivation period. Therefore, it is useful to find functions that approximate the reference absorbance of the spectrophotometer based on the measured data as well as possible. To find these functions, Figure 3.17 shows the reference absorbance measured with the spectrophotometer plotted against the on-line measurement data of the sensor at the time of off-line sampling. In Figure 3.17 a) the absorbance calculated from the transmission signal of the sensor is plotted on the x-axis. As previously observed in Figure 3.16, it can also be seen in Figure 3.17 that the absorbance measured with the sensor reacts more sensitively to changes in the reference absorbance at low biomass concentrations. At higher concentrations, the sensitivity decreases progressively, which is reflected in the graph by a steeper increase in the reference absorbance. This curve of absorbance as a function of biomass concentration for *C. vulgaris* has also been reported in the literature [26, 78]. It is evident that the linear Lambert-Beer law is not suitable to approximate this nonlinear curve and could be used only at low concentrations [26]. Instead, a hyperbolic model, for

example, is suitable for fitting such a curve [26]. The regression using a hyperbolic model is shown in 3.17 a) as a black dash-dotted line. As can be seen, the hyperbolic model approximates the relationship between absorbance of the sensor and the reference spectrophotometer very well. To obtain a measure of quality for the nonlinear regression, the root-mean-square error (*RMSE*) is calculated for the fitting of the reference absorbance by the sensor absorbance via the hyperbolic model (*RMSE*= 0.2).

In Figure 3.17 b) the opacity is plotted on the x-axis and the data points are shown as blue squares and in Figure 3.17 c) the side scatter signal is plotted on the x-axis and the data points are shown as red triangles. As previously observed in Figure 3.16, side scatter signal and opacity behave similarly and follow the reference absorbance more directly than the sensor absorbance calculated from the opacity. In Figure 3.17 b) and c), this is reflected in the fact that a roughly linear relationship can be observed between reference absorbance and opacity or the side scatter signal. The linear regression lines of the opacity and the side scatter signal are shown in Figure 3.17 b) and c) by blue and red dashed lines, respectively ($r^2 = 0.986$ and *RMSE*= 0.35 and $r^2 = 0.984$ and *RMSE*= 0.42). However, for both opacity and side scatter signal, it is observed that the linear regression underestimates the reference absorbance and biomass, for a reference absorbance below about 4.5. In contrast, in the range between 4.5 and 9.5, the linear calibration would slightly overestimate the reference absorbance. In order to better approximate this course of the opacity and the side scatter signal, a linear regression with a third-degree polynomial is therefore applied in addition. The result of this regression is shown in Figure 3.17 b) and c) by a blue and a red dotted line, respectively. Due to the higher flexibility of the third-degree polynomial regression, the course of the opacity and the side scatter signal can be approximated more accurately ($r^2 = 0.996$ and *RMSE*= 0.2 and $r^2 = 0.997$ and *RMSE*= 0.17, respectively). However, the measured reference absorbance is increasingly inaccurate from the fourth day onwards, as can be seen from the vertical error bars shown in Figure 3.17. Therefore, it has to be investigated by further experiments whether the relation between reference absorbance and opacity or side scatter signal should indeed be represented by a third-degree polynomial or whether this leads to overfitting. In addition, it must be investigated whether the correlation between sensor measurement signal and reference absorbance is reproducible between different cultivations.

For this purpose, the second cultivation of *C. vulgaris* in the photobioreactor (*PBR2*) is considered below. The measured values can be used to investigate whether the

Figure 3.17: Fitting of the sensor signals of the 780 nm LED (x-axis) to the absorbance measured off-line with the spectrophotometer at 780 nm (y-axis, reference to biomass) during cultivation *PBR1*. a): Absorbance of the sensor (black circles) and fitting with hyperbolic function (black dotted line, $RMSE= 0.2$). b): opacity of the sensor (blue squares) and fitting with straight line (blue dashed, $RMSE= 0.35$) and third-degree polynomial (blue dotted, $RMSE= 0.2$), c): side scatter signal (red triangles) and fitting with straight line (red dashed, $RMSE= 0.42$) and third-degree polynomial (red dotted, $RMSE= 0.17$).

calibration curves found in 3.17 are applicable to further experiments to estimate the biomass concentration. The reproducibility of this relationship is very important to be able to use the sensor in industrial applications. For this purpose, in Figure 3.18, the reference absorbance at 780 nm measured during the second cultivation *PBR2* with the spectrophotometer is plotted in the upper diagrams over the signals of the on-line sensor measured with the 780 nm LED. Furthermore, selected calibration curves previously determined in Figure 3.17 for the other cultivation *PBR1* are shown by discontinuous lines in the upper diagrams. In the lower diagrams, the absolute error between the calibration curves of the first cultivation *PBR1* and the measured data of the second cultivation *PBR2* is shown. For this purpose, the residual, which is the difference between the actually measured reference absorbance and the reference absorbance estimated with the calibration curve, is shown in the lower diagrams and refers to its respective diagram above.

In Figure 3.18 a) the absorbance of the sensor is plotted on the x-axis and in the upper diagram the hyperbolic calibration curve is shown with a dash dot line. To obtain a measure of the applicability of the calibration curve to the new data, the root-mean-square error is again evaluated. The root-mean-square error of the hyperbolic calibration of the absorbance is $RMSE=1.09$. As can be seen in Figure 3.18 a) in the lower plot, the residual is close to zero at a low absorbance and increases with increasing absorbance. Therefore, the calibration curve increasingly underestimates the reference absorbance as the reference absorbance increases. The error is amplified by the large slope of the calibration curve at a high absorbance or biomass concentration. This is a disadvantage when using the absorbance measured with the sensor to estimate the biomass at high biomass concentrations. In Figure 3.18 b), the opacity measured during the second cultivation *PBR2* is plotted on the x-axis. In the upper plot, the corresponding measured reference absorbance is shown as blue squares. The absorbance estimated with the calibration line from the first cultivation is shown as a blue dashed line. As can be seen, the reference absorbance is underestimated by the linear calibration curve. In the lower plot of Figure 3.18 b) it can be observed that the residual is relatively large except for very small opacities. This leads to a $RMSE= 1.15$. The third-degree polynomial regression curve describes the new points a little worse ($RMSE= 1.17$) and is not shown. In Figure 3.18 c), the side scatter signal measured during the second cultivation is plotted on the x-axis and in the upper plot the corresponding measured reference absorbance is shown as red triangles. Furthermore, the reference absorbance estimated by the calibration curve obtained from the first cultivation is shown as a red dashed line. In the lower plot of Figure 3.18 c) it

can be seen that the residual reaches a maximum at a medium side scatter signal. In contrast, at low and high side scatter signal, the biomass is better approximated. This leads to an overall root-mean-square error of $RMSE = 0.65$. Also for the side scatter signal, the third-degree polynomial regression achieves a slightly worse approximation than the simple linear regression ($RMSE = 0.76$) and is therefore not shown.

From the test it is demonstrated that the calibration curves obtained in advance can qualitatively estimate the course of the biomass concentration well, even for new measurement data. However, in all three examples the true biomass concentration is underestimated by the calibration curves. This underestimation is up to 15% of the maximal reference absorbance and biomass concentration for the absorbance and opacity. For the calibration line of the side scatter signal, this maximum underestimation is about 10% of the maximal biomass concentration. As shown before, the $RMSE$ when using the calibration curve of the side scatter signal is about less than 60% of the $RMSE$ calculated for absorbance and opacity when the calibrations curves are applied to the other cultivation. Considering the limited amount of data and limited choice of calibration models, this suggests that for reproducible estimation of biomass concentration the side scatter signal with a linear calibration should be used. However, further cultivations need to be performed to confirm this assumption. The additional data thus obtained can then be used to generate more meaningful calibration curves based on a larger data base.

In order to improve the functionality of the sensor, it is necessary to find out how the variation of the functional relationship between the sensor measurement signals and the reference absorbance shown in 3.18 arises. In Figure 3.16 it was shown by smooth curves that there is low noise in the sensor data and in Figure 3.18 it can be seen that the residual or the error has the same sign for all measurement points. Therefore, it is unlikely that the deviation can be explained by any random noise underlying the sensor measurements. Instead, the relationship between reference absorbance and scatter per biomass measured with the sensor changes systematically. One possible explanation is that the reference spectrophotometer measurement differs between the two cultivations. Since the same methodology was always used, this is unlikely. Nevertheless, a significantly larger standard deviation of the reference absorbance over three samples was measured for the *PBR1* cultivation than for *PBR2*, as can be seen by comparing the error bars in Figure 3.18 with Figure 3.17. Another possible explanation is related to the sensor itself. It is possible that the intensity of the 780 nm LED changed in different ways during the cultivations. To verify this, the intensity of the LED during

Figure 3.18: Testing of the biomass calibration curves previously obtained from cultivation *PBR1* on new data from cultivation *PBR2* of *C. vulgaris* in the photobioreactor. Upper graphs: off-line absorbance of spectrophotometer vs. sensor signal. Symbols: measured data, lines: estimated curves based on calibration. Lower diagrams: residual (measured value - estimated value). a), b) and c): comparison of absorbance (black, hyperbolic model), opacity (blue, linear) and side scatter signal (red, linear) measured by the on-line sensor.

cultivation would have to be measured independently of the microalgal suspensions. In addition, temperature influences could play a role, since intensity of the LEDs and sensitivity of the photodiodes are temperature dependent [70]. However, first investigations have shown that the temperature influence is only small (data not shown). Another possible explanation for the limited reproducibility of the correlation between sensor signal and reference is based on the optical properties of the microalgae suspension. In this work, it is simplistically assumed that the scattering properties of individual cells do not change during growth and that the absorbance spectrum changes only due to the mass of cells per total volume and their pigment concentration. However, in reality, when the average size, shape, and internal structure of microalgae change, the optical properties of the suspension are expected to change as well [32, 38]. Thus, the reduced reproducibility of the found correlations could also be explained by biological differences between the both cultivations. And these morphological differences may not be represented by the models used based on few measurement variables.

It can be summarized that with the newly developed sensor it is possible to approximate the absorbance measured under dilution with the off-line spectrophotometer and thus indirectly the biomass concentration. The side scatter signal or the transmission signal in the form of opacity or absorbance can be used for this purpose. First calibration curves show qualitatively good results, but these have to be improved by further measurements and reasons for the slightly limited reproducibility between multiple longtime cultivations have to be investigated in more detail.

3.4.2 On-line approximation of pigment content

After showing that the biomass concentration can be approximated with the readings of the newly developed on-line flow-through sensor, it will be investigated whether the newly developed sensor is suitable to detect changes in the pigment content of the cells. For this purpose, the two *C. vulgaris* cultivations in the photobioreactor *PBR1* and *PBR2* already discussed in Chapter 3.4.1 will be considered again. As reported in Chapter 2.3.2, direct determination of pigments is very time consuming as the pigments would have to be extracted from the cells for this purpose. Instead, as also applied in Chapter 3.1, the off-line reference absorbance measured with the spectrophotometer is used as a measure of pigment content. For this purpose, the reference absorbance at 505 nm for estimating the carotenoid content and at 690 nm

for estimating the chlorophyll a content, respectively, is divided by the absorbance at 780 nm. It is assumed, based on the considerations described in Chapter 3.1, that this is a measure of pigment content per biomass. Unlike the off-line measurement, the suspension cannot be diluted in the on-line sensor. So, the measurement is outside the range of validity of the Lambert-Beer law and the absorbance is not linear to biomass, as shown previously in Figure 3.17. In Chapter 3.4.1 it has been shown that the opacity, in contrast to the absorbance, behaves approximately linear to the biomass concentration over a larger biomass concentration range. For easier interpretation of the results, the pigment content per biomass is therefore expressed in the following not by the ratio of the absorbances measured with the sensor but by the ratio of the opacities measured with the sensor. The time course of these measurement data of the cultivation in the photobioreactor *PBR2* is shown in Figure 3.19. On the left y-axis, the relative opacity measured with the on-line sensor is plotted and shown as a green dotted line for the 505 nm LED and a red dashed line for the 690 nm LED, respectively. It can be seen that the relative signal for both LEDs is approximately constant at value of one until the second day. Then the relative opacity for both wavelengths increases abruptly to a value of two by about the fourth day. With increasing cultivation time, the relative opacity calculated from the sensor signals at both 690 nm and 505 nm decreases approximately exponentially from the fourth and fifth day, respectively. After 20 days, the opacity ratio with 505 nm reaches again at a value of one, while the opacity ratio with 690 nm decreases to a value of 0.7.

To validate this sensor measurement result, Figure 3.19 plots on the right y-axis the ratio of relative absorbance measured with the spectrophotometer. The data points of the spectrometer measurements at 505 nm are shown as green squares and the data points at 690 nm are shown as red triangles. For both wavelengths, it can be seen that the spectrophotometer measurement, which serves as a reference, also shows a similar curve to that of the sensor. For both wavelengths, the spectrophotometer also shows an increase in the measurement signal from the start of cultivation to the fifth day, with the relative absorbance reaching a higher value at 505 nm. And also, as with the relative opacity measured with the sensor, a roughly exponential decrease from the fifth to the nineteenth day can be observed for the relative reference absorbance of both wavelengths. From both the sensor data and the spectrophotometer data, it can be seen in Figure 3.19 that after five days of cultivation, the condition of the microalgae changes and this appears to be expressed by a switch from an increasing pigment content per biomass to a decreasing pigment content per biomass. In the sensor data in Figure 3.19, it can be seen that this change occurs about one day later when measured

Figure 3.19: Estimation of time course of pigment content per biomass during cultivation *PBR2* of *C. vulgaris* in photobioreactor. Signals are divided by their respective signal at 780 nm. Left y-axis: opacity measured with on-line sensor in bypass (lines) at 505 nm (green dotted) and 690 nm (red dashed). Right y-axis: absorbance measured with off-line spectrophotometer (symbols) at 505 nm (green squares) and 690 nm (red triangles). Cultivation conditions: 23°C and continuous light.

with the 505 nm LED than with 690 nm. It is assumed that the relative opacity at 505 nm is a measure of carotenoid content and 690 nm is a measure of chlorophyll a content. Therefore, the sensor data indicate that chlorophyll a content increases one day earlier while carotenoids are still being formed. This could be related to the fact that microalgae produce carotenoids in excess under suboptimal conditions as reported in Chapter 2.2.1 [48]. Furthermore, the temporal offset of the begin of decrease of the different pigments is an indication that the decrease is not due to contamination with microorganisms that do not perform photosynthesis. Otherwise, the content of both pigments would start to decrease at the same time. With semiquantitative measurement of nitrate content using test strips, it can be observed that nitrate is

depleted around the fourth day of cultivation in the photobioreactor (data not shown). Furthermore, a decreasing chlorophyll a content per biomass under nitrogen starvation was reported in the literature [32]. Therefore, the peak of 690 nm measured with sensor and the spectrophotometer after five days of cultivation can probably be attributed to a change of state of microalgae due to nitrogen limitation. In this context, it is highly interesting that also when monitoring the biomass, as exemplarily shown for both cultivations in the photobioreactor on the basis of Figure 3.16, a delay in the growth curve can be detected between the fourth and the sixth day and this can possibly be explained by a change in the metabolism. According to this theory, the altered metabolism of the microalgae caused by nitrogen limitation leads to reduced pigment formation. And it is important to note that both the slowed growth and the reduced pigment formation could then be recorded with the sensor. This is an important indication that the newly developed sensor already represents a useful addition to the monitoring of microalgae in its current state of development.

In Figure 3.19 it was found that the relative opacity curve measured with the sensor can qualitatively mirror the relative absorbance curve measured with the spectrophotometer and thus could also provide a quantitative measure of pigment content per biomass. In the following, the correlation between the two types of signals is investigated and it will be examined if a calibration curve can be found. For this purpose, Figure 3.20 plots the absorbance measured with the spectrophotometer over the on-line measured relative opacity at the time of the respective off-line sampling. Figure 3.20 a) shows the result when measured with 505 nm for both performed photobioreactor cultivations *PBR1* and *PBR2* of *C. vulgaris*. The measured data of the cultivation *PBR2* previously considered in Figure 3.19 are shown with green squares and one can see a linear relationship. This is confirmed by a linear regression shown in Figure 3.20 a) as a green dashed line ($r^2 = 0.85$). In addition, in Figure 3.20 a) the measured data of the other photobioreactor cultivation of *C. vulgaris* (*PBR1*) also at 505 nm are shown by blue empty squares. The calibration curve that is being searched for must be valid for replicates of the experiment so that in the future, when monitoring the microalgae, quantitative conclusions can be made about the pigment content without having to perform an off-line measurement. Therefore, a linear regression is calculated that takes into account the data points from both experiments. The result of this regression is shown in 3.20 a) as a black dotted line. The coefficient of determination, and thus the goodness of fit of the regression, drops significantly in this case ($r^2 = 0.64$).

In Figure 3.20 b), the correlation for 690 nm is examined. There, the readings at

690 nm of the cultivation *PBR2* previously discussed in 3.19 are shown by red triangles. Their linear regression is shown as a red dashed line and has the same coefficient of determination as the regression at 505 nm of cultivation *PBR2* ($r^2 = 0.85$). The data points of the other cultivation *PBR2* at 690, nm are shown as blue empty triangles in Figure 3.20 b). As with 505 nm, a further regression of all data point pairs at 690 nm from both experiments is performed. This is shown as a black dotted line in Figure 3.20 b) and models the relationship between relative reference absorbance and relative opacity measured with the sensor slightly better than in the case of 505 nm, manifesting itself in a higher coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.71$). Through this investigation, it is shown that for data of the cultivation *PBR2* shown in Figure 3.19, the relationship between relative opacity measured with the sensor and relative reference absorbance measured with the spectrophotometer within a cultivation can be approximated relatively well by a linear function. However, it is disclosed that it is problematic to transfer this found relationship to the other cultivation, since the spread of the data point pairs increases. And therefore, due to the assumed linear relationship between relative opacity and relative absorbance, it is limited to reproducibly determine the pigment content quantitatively between different experiments. As an attempt to explain this, the considerations on the reason for the reduced reproducibility introduced earlier in Chapter 3.4.1 can also be used here. Thus, it cannot be determined at this point whether there is a technical or biological cause.

Figure 3.20: Correlation between the absorbance measured with the spectrophotometer and the relative opacity measured with the on-line sensor, each related to the simultaneously measured value at 780 nm for two cultivations of *C. vulgaris* *PBR1* and *PBR2*. a): 505 nm in *PBR2* (green squares, green dashed linear regression, $r^2 = 0.85$) and *PBR1* (empty squares), linear regression over all data points (black dotted line, $r^2 = 0.64$), b): 690 nm in *PBR2* (red triangles, red dashed linear regression, $r^2 = 0.85$) and *PBR1* (empty triangles), linear regression over all data points (black dotted line, $r^2 = 0.71$).

4 Conclusion and outlook

4.1 Conclusion

Large-scale production with microalgae needs to become more efficient to make sustainable products from microalgae competitive. Monitoring and control based on software sensors can contribute to this. The aim of this work was to develop a multi-wavelength optical flow-through cell sensor that can be used for on-line monitoring of microalgae. In the future, data measured by this sensor shall be used together with software sensor tools to estimate the biological process variables that are difficult to measure directly.

To establish a knowledge base on the wavelength-dependent optical behavior of microalgae, shake flask samples of *C. vulgaris* were studied using off-line UV-Vis spectrophotometry. Based on these results, a concept for the development of the multi-wavelength optical flow-through cell sensor was created and the sensor was constructed by rapid prototyping using 3D printing. The functionality of the multi-wavelength optical flow-through cell sensor was then evaluated by manual off-line measurement of chemicals. For this purpose, ink from fountain pen cartridges and the turbidity calibration standard formazin were used in different concentrations. Finally, the newly developed multi-wavelength optical flow-through cell sensor was tested during two *C. vulgaris* cultivations in the bypass of a photobioreactor.

Using wavelength scans of the *C. vulgaris* samples from shake flasks and comparison with values from the literature, the peaks of absorbance measured with the off-line spectrophotometer could be traced back to pigment absorption maxima. The peak at 500 nm could be explained by the absorption of the carotenoids β -carotene and lutein and the peak at 686 nm with the absorption of chlorophyll a.

Motivated by these results, a 505 nm LED for monitoring carotenoid concentration, a

690 nm LED for monitoring chlorophyll a concentration, and a 780 nm LED for monitoring biomass concentration were selected, taking into account commercial availability. A modified 10 mm path length standard polystyrene cuvette was used as the flow-through cell. Furthermore, a housing geometry was designed using rapid prototyping to allow measurement of the transmission (0°) of the side scatter (90°) and the backscatter (160°) of all three LEDs with a total of three photodiodes. In addition, measurement software was developed in Python to control the LEDs individually, to make the measurement process flexible and to store the data in an easily accessible format.

By off-line evaluation of the newly developed sensor with ink, it was shown that the sensor can determine the concentration of dye solutions by measuring the absorbance as accurately as using an off-line spectrophotometer ($r^2 = 0.999$). Evaluation with formazin demonstrated, that backscatter measurement with the current sensor setup is not suitable for determining the formazin concentrations studied. However, it was found that there is a strict linear relationship between the particle concentration of the formazin suspension and the measured side scatter signal as well as absorbance up to a concentration of at least 260 NTU and 400 NTU, respectively ($r^2 = 0.999$). These experiments with chemicals proved, that the sensor can be used in off-line operation to determine the concentration of absorbing or scattering samples very accurately, thus fulfilling an important requirement for its further use.

After this demonstration of basic functionality, the multi-wavelength optical flow-through cell sensor was used to monitor two photobioreactor cultivations of *C. vulgaris* on-line. During the 17- and 21-day cultivations, the sensor was able to continuously record measurement data without any water leakage or biofilm formation observed in the self-designed flow-through cell. In addition, the measurement signals showed low noise compared to the signal change. The sensor data could be used to approximate the off-line readings of the spectrophotometer as a demonstration for future applications. The biomass related reference absorbance at 780 nm could be approximated by linear functions of side scatter or opacity ($r^2 = 0.984$, $r^2 = 0.986$) while for the sensor absorbance a hyperbolic model was used. Furthermore, it was found that the ratio of reference absorbances related to the specific pigment content could be approximated by a linear function of the opacity ratio ($r^2 = 0.85$). The application of the found correlations to the measurement data of another cultivation was error-prone. The reason could not yet be clarified and is thus the subject of future research.

By estimating biological process variables using simple models, the potential of the

sensor measurement data was demonstrated. Thus, it was shown that the optical flow-through cell sensor developed in this work provides the hardware to develop software sensor strategies for monitoring microalgae.

4.2 Outlook

In the next steps, it should be investigated whether the quantitative difference of the correlation between sensor signal and reference also occurs in additional cultivations. If this is the case, the cause and significance of this difference between the sensor signal and reference measurements have to be identified. The crucial question here is, whether the cause of the differences lies in changed properties of the multi-wavelength optical flow-through cell sensor and consequently has a technical reason. Possible technical causes in this case would be slightly changed angles during reassembly of the sensor when preparing for a cultivation or changed characteristics of the electronic components. For example, the performance of both photodiodes and LEDs is temperature dependent. Therefore, it might be reasonable that in the future temperature in the vicinity of LEDs and photodiodes is also measured with the sensor to use it for data analysis [19, 20]. In order to be able to perceive a possible drift of the LED intensity during long-term measurements, the use of a reference photodiode could also be useful [20]. Whether these measures are necessary can be investigated relatively easily in the future by off-line long-term measurements of an empty cuvette.

On the other hand, the reduced reproducibility of the correlation between sensor signal and reference during different long-time cultivations could also be due to a biological rather than technical reason. Because, if the average morphology of the cells changes, the specific optical properties of the microalgae will also change [32, 38]. In this case, the simple calibration models employed so far would have to be replaced by calibration models reflecting such changes. However, it is difficult to measure changes in the morphology directly with an optical sensor [17]. In flow cytometry, cell size is approximated by the forward scatter signal at an angle less than 20° [38, 58]. It is possible that the measurement principle of forward scatter can be transferred to the optical sensor developed here and used in the future. However, this would probably require a more focused light, like that of a laser module [41, 73]. In addition, the measurement system could be supplemented by light sources with further wavelengths such as 650 nm for the estimation of the chlorophyll b concentration [66]. Furthermore,

the measurement principle of fluorescence could be integrated into the sensor system to collect more information about the pigment content [21].

As soon as it is clear from the previous considerations, that long-term measurements are reproducible from a technical point of view, the labor-intensive calibration can begin using directly measured biological variables such as biomass dry weight and pigment concentration. More complex models will probably be needed to account for cell morphology in this process [40, 79]. These will likely handle multiple measured variables and possibly also take into account their course over time. This would bring the project to a stage where the signals from the multi-wavelength optical flow-through cell sensor developed in this work feed the data processing of a software sensor. The software sensor can then be trained to approximate on-line difficult-to-measure biological process variables and thus contribute to the sustainable and efficient production of low value-added products by controlling the state of microalgae cultures.

5 Appendix

5.1 Methods

Microalgal strains and culture conditions

Cultivation in shake flasks

Stock cultures of *C. vulgaris* (SAG 211-11b) were transferred every 15 days and used as a starting material. These stock cultures were kept at 25 ± 2 °C, 100 rpm on an IKA KS 260 basic shaker, and under continuous light (2700 K, $120 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). Inoculums were cultivated in baffled shake flasks (250 mL) containing 50 mL of autoclaved BBM medium (pH 6.5) for 12 days.

Off-line multi-wavelength scan experiments

Main cultivation flasks of *C. vulgaris* were inoculated with 2 mL of physiologically active inoculum. This aliquot was transferred into baffled shake flasks (500 mL) containing 100 mL of autoclaved BBM medium (pH 6.5). Three samples of 1.5 mL each were taken at each sampling point under aseptic conditions. Off-line measurements were performed at days 3, 5, 8, 13, 18 or 19 and 21. These sampling points were chosen to meet different physiological cell growth phases. Wavelength scans from 350 nm to 900 nm were performed with a UV-Vis spectrophotometer Libra S50 (Biochrom Ltd) using 3 mL transparent polystyrol cuvettes (SARSTEDT 67.742) with a path length of 10 mm. First a blank with the corresponding medium was measured. Then microalgae samples were diluted with medium to an absorbance below 0.5 to stay in the validity range of the Lambert-Beer law [19, 41]. The measured absorbance was then multiplied

with the dilution factor to obtain the absorbance value of the undiluted sample. Finally, the mean (Equation 5.1) and sample standard deviation (Equation 5.2) over all three samples of each sampling point were calculated [80].

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad (5.1)$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (5.2)$$

Flow-through optical sensor development and testing

Rapid prototyping via 3D printing

Rapid prototyping techniques were used to build the housing of the sensor. For this the CAD software Inventor 2023 by AutoCAD was used to generate 3D models of the construction. After that, printing procedures were calculated from the 3D models with the software PrusaSlicer 2.5.0 (Prusa Research). These printing procedures were executed with a 3D printer Prusa i3 MK3S+ (Prusa Research) to print the components of the sensor housing.

Manufacture of the flow-through cell

A 4 mL cuvette made of polystyrene (SARSTEDT 67.754) with a path length of 10 mm was used to make the flow-through. This was modified on the lathe into a flow-through cell by cutting off its bottom. Connecting the cuvette to the bypass is a challenge. Sealing rings cannot be used with the rectangular shape. An other attempt was to make a connection using a 3D-printed adapter that is glued to the cuvette. However, the printed mold was found to leak as soon as pressure was applied to the water content. Therefore, silicone plugs were used in the flow-through cell as adapters between the rectangular cuvette and the tubes. The molding silicone rubber for tin casting type 3

HB (Troll Factory Rainer Habekost e.K.) with a Shore hardness of A 33 was used to manufacture the silicone plugs. Its two components were weighed with the precision balance Entris® II Essential Line (Sartorius AG) to mix them in the ratio of 1:1 as described by the manufacturer. The two components were mixed with a spatula for at least one minute and care was taken to not trap air bubbles. At least 10 min after mixing, the compound was poured into a mold. This mold consisted of a 3D printed object into which a standard cuvette, open on both sides, was inserted. In this way, the inner contour of the cuvette was molded and the silicone plug was provided with a bigger cylindrical contact surface.

Electronical setup

In order to be able to operate the sensor, a controllable current source for the power supply of the LEDs on the one hand and on the other hand measurement electronics, which transmits the signal of the photodiodes to the computer, were developed. The analog output module ICP CON M-7028 CR (ICPDAS-EUROPE GmbH) was used as the current source. Via the serial interface with the computer, current levels between 0 and 20 mA could be flexibly set at the eight analog outputs of the module. Thus it was suitable for the operation of LEDs. The measurement electronics for reading out the photodiode signal consisted of a 16-bit A/D converter and a microcontroller. A current is generated in the photodiode by the incoming photons, which is converted into a voltage by the photodiode chip. This voltage was converted by the 16-bit A/D converter into an analog signal with the maximum value of 32676. The microcontroller Parallax Propeller P8X32A (Parallax Inc.) was used to read the analog value provided by the A/D converter and communicate it to the computer (HP 250 G6, Windows 10 Pro).

Data management

For the data analysis and graph plotting the software JupyterLab from the company Project Jupyter was used. It was started from the software distribution Miniconda with a virtual environment that contains Python 3.8.12.

General procedure for off-line measurements with the sensor

For manual off-line experiments the sensor was placed in a vertical position and the liquid was pushed into the flow-through cell via a syringe until it left the upper side. This was done gently to avoid remaining gas bubbles [73]. Then the measurement was started. After the measurement, the liquid was pulled out of the cuvette with a syringe. When many samples were measured it was started with the blank reference sample which was either the medium or pure water. After that, each set of samples with the next lowest concentration was measured to reduce the backmixing error from remaining liquids. After an experiment, the flow-through was opened and washed with isopropanol (70 % V/V) and deionized water.

Ink experiment using off-line measurements

Ink from fountain pen cartridges ('Königsblau', Pelikan Group GmbH) was used to validate the sensor measurement by a colored liquid without particles. A stock solution (C_{stock}) with 10 % (V/V) of pure ink was prepared using deionized water. With this stock solution further dilutions with deionized water were prepared. The concentrations relative to the stock solution are shown in Table 5.1. In this way three samples for each concentration level were prepared. For every sample, 28 measurement points were performed with the sensor. Furthermore, the measurement of one sample was repeated three times to blank out the error from the dilution process. The sensor configuration is shown in Table 5.9.

Formazin experiment using off-line measurements

Formazin was used to evaluate the response of the sensor on suspensions. Formazin was prepared by following the recipe from [81]. Two solutions were prepared for this purpose. In the first solution 10 g of hexamethylenetetramine was dissolved in ultra-pure water and was filled up to 100 mL with ultra-pure water. In the second solution 1 g of hydrazine sulfate was dissolved in ultra-pure water and was then filled up to 100 mL with ultra-pure water. A 50 mL volume of these solutions were then mixed with each other in a 1 L amber bottle which was protected by light with aluminum foil. This solution was stirred on a magnetic stirrer for 24 hours. The solution was then filled up to 1 L

Table 5.1: List of ink concentrations

Name	Concentration relative to the original ink ($\frac{c}{c_{ink}}$)	Fraction relative to highest measured concentration ($\frac{c}{c_{max}}$)
c_{ink}	1	
c_{stock}	$\frac{1}{10}$	
c_{max}	$\frac{1}{80}$	1
p	$\frac{1}{160}$	$\frac{1}{2}$
q	$\frac{1}{240}$	$\frac{1}{3}$
r	$\frac{1}{320}$	$\frac{1}{4}$
s	$\frac{1}{640}$	$\frac{1}{8}$
t	$\frac{1}{1280}$	$\frac{1}{16}$
u	$\frac{1}{2560}$	$\frac{1}{32}$
v	$\frac{1}{5120}$	$\frac{1}{64}$
w	$\frac{1}{10240}$	$\frac{1}{128}$
x	$\frac{1}{20480}$	$\frac{1}{256}$

Table 5.2: Sensor configuration of ink experiment

Component	Realisation
LEDs	625 nm (1.55 mA)
photodiodes	OPT101 (transmission), SD (side scatter)
Current source	Black electronic and measurement device
Data logger	Propeller data logger

with ultra-pure water to achieve a stock solution with a turbidity of 400 NTU. From this stock solution, dilutions of 2 NTU, 10 NTU, 20 NTU, 40 NTU, 100 NTU, 200 NTU, 260 NTU were prepared. Every dilution was prepared in triplicate. The measurements were done from the lowest concentrations to the highest concentrations. The sensor setup for the experiment with formazin is shown in Table 5.3.

On-line sensor evaluation in a lab-scale photobioreactor using living cells

The used photobioreactor system was developed in the Institute for Technical Chemistry (TCI) at the University of Hanover. A schematic representation of the photobioreactor

Table 5.3: Sensor configuration of formazin experiment

Setting	Specification
Measurement modes	Transmission, 505 nm, 1.5 mA Transmission, 690 nm, 3.6 mA Transmission, 780 nm, 9 mA Side scatter, 505 nm, 1.7 mA Side scatter, 690 nm, 4 mA Side scatter, 780 nm, 20 mA Back scatter, 505 nm, 0.15 mA Back scatter, 690 nm, 0.35 mA Back scatter, 780 nm, 1.5 mA
LED in central position	780 nm
Photodiodes	OPT101 (transmission), SD (side scatter), SD (backscatter)
Current source	ICP COM M-7028
Data logger	Propeller data logger

system can be found in Figure 5.1. The photobioreactor system consists of a cultivation vessel (black, 1), a bypass line (green, 2 - 5) and a gas supply system (blue, 6 - 9).

Microalgae grew in a 500 mL cultivation vessel exposed to direct and continuous light. This vessel is marked with (1) in the schematic view 5.1 and is shown as a photo in Figure 5.2. The cap of the cultivation vessel had four openings, which were used for inlet and outlet of the gas, and the inlet and outlet of the cultivation broth. The cultivation vessel was stirred at 240 rpm using a magnetic stirrer. Furthermore the cultivation vessel was surrounded by two flat LED lamps (OPT 5902, 10 W, 2700 K, with an additional matt plastic screen) with a spacing of 3 cm on each side. The light emitting surfaces had a width of 3 cm and a length of 6 cm. The light intensity on the surface of the glass vessel was $1020 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, the light loss on the vessel glass wall was $280 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

The gas supply path is shown in Figure 5.1 in blue. It was used to feed the cultivation vessel with 50.5 mL min^{-1} of CO_2 -enriched and humidified air. For that, 50 mL min^{-1} air was mixed with 0.5 mL min^{-1} CO_2 in a gas mixing device (6). After the gases were mixed, the gas mixture passed through a humidifying vessel filled with acidified distilled water (7). Humidification was intended to prevent water losses from the cultivation vessel by the gas stream. After the humidification, the gas was filter-sterilized ($0.22 \mu\text{m}$) before it entered into the cultivation vessel (8). A sparger was used inside the cultivation vessel to improve gas mass transfer. After rising through the liquid phase of the cultivation vessel, the gas left the vessel via the outlet in the

Figure 5.1: Scheme of the used photobioreactor system. Central element was the illuminated reactor vessel (1). The bypass loop (green) contained a peristaltic pump (2), a degassing vessel (3), the sensor unit (4) and a cooling bath that removed heat Q (5). The gas supply path (blue) contained a gas mixing device (6), a humidifying vessel (7), a sterile filter (8) and a leakage test vessel (9).

cap and flowed into a open flask (9) which was filled with acidified water.

The other two openings in the lid of the culture vessel corresponded to the inlet and outlet of the bypass loop. In Figure 5.1 the bypass loop is shown in green. The culture broth with the microalgae was transported through the bypass with the use of a peristaltic pump (iPump2S® with YZ15A head, Signal Fluid, (2)) with the flow rate of 60 mL min^{-1} . After the peristaltic pump, the liquid passed three more stages in the bypass. First it entered the degassing vessel (3) in which the liquid and gas bubbles separate from each other. The outlet hose of this degassing vessel protruded to the vessel's bottom such that only the liquid phase could exit the degassing vessel. This

Figure 5.2: Cultivation vessel setup.

degassing vessel was stirred by a magnetic stirrer at 180 rpm to avoid the sedimentation of the microalgae. After the degassing vessel the liquid passes through the sensor system (4). The sensor system was aligned in a way such that the culture broth flowed in it vertically to avoid the sedimentation of microalgae and to avoid the accumulation of gas bubbles. Then the culture broth flowed to a cooling bath set at 15 °C. The cooling bath was used to keep the temperature in the cultivation vessel at about 23 °C. The temperature of the cultivation vessel was measured manually by a infrared thermometer P 4980 (PeakTech Prüf- und Messtechnik GmbH).

The different components of the photobioreactor system (bottles, lids, tubing) were steam sterilized for 40 min at 100 °C. It was not possible to use a higher temperature because the material of modified cultivation vessel lid could otherwise deform. After the sterilization, the reactor system was further assembled under aseptic conditions. The interior of the sensor flow-through was disinfected with isopropanol (70 % V/V) for one minute and afterwards three times flushed with distilled and sterilized water. Then, it was inserted into the bypass loop of the photobioreactor under aseptic conditions. The medium for *C. vulgaris* was autoclaved at 121 °C for 30 min. Then, under aseptic conditions, 600 mL of the medium was filled into the cultivation vessel and 100 mL medium was filled into the degassing vessel.

After the photobioreactor system has been assembled and set up with the measurement electronics, the peristaltic pump was turned on and the blank was measured for at least 12 hours to see if there were no leaks and if the sensor measurement worked as expected. Thereafter, 5 mL of a 12 days preculture were inoculated in the cultivation vessel via a syringe and the gas flux was turned on. The needle was sterilized by the flame of a Bunsen burner before the injection. The inoculation took place over the gas outlet of the cultivation vessel from which the outgoing tubing was removed for the procedure of inoculation and afterwards it was cleaned with isopropanol and was reattached to its original position. Samples for off-line measurements were taken directly after the inoculation and at days 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 10, 11, 13, 14 for the cultivation *PBR1* and at the days 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 10, 13, 14, 15, 17, 19 for the cultivation *PBR2*. For sampling a 15 cm long metal capillary on top of the syringe was used to reach the liquid level in the cultivation vessel. The sensor configuration of the monitoring of the photobioreactor cultivations can be seen in Table 5.4.

Table 5.4: Sensor configuration of monitoring in bypass of photobioreactor

Setting	Specification
Measurement modes	Transmission, 505nm, 1.31mA, Transmission, 690 nm, 1.78 mA Transmission, 780 nm, 2.55 mA 780nm, 0.35mA, sidescatter 780nm, 0.35mA, backscatter
LED in central position	780 nm
Photodiodes	OPT101 (transmission), SD (side scatter), SD (backscatter)
Current source	ICP COM M-7028
Data logger	Propeller data logger

Functions for calibration

Different types of calibration curves were used to fit the sensor data to the spectrophotometer absorbance. These are shown in the equations 5.3 - 5.6. The parameters found for fitting the spectrometer absorbance within the cultivation *PBR1* shown in Figure 3.17 are displayed in Table 5.5.

$$\text{linear (fixed)} \quad f(x, a) = a \cdot (1 - x) \quad (5.3)$$

$$\text{linear} \quad f(x, a, b) = a \cdot x + b \quad (5.4)$$

$$\text{polynomial} \quad f(x, a, b, c, d) = ax^3 + bx^2 + cx + d \quad (5.5)$$

$$\text{hyperbolic} \quad f(x, a, b) = \frac{x}{b \cdot (a - x)} \quad (5.6)$$

Table 5.5: List of regression formulas found in Figure 3.17.

application	model	formula
side scatter	linear	$f(x) = 0.001405 \cdot x + 0.1814$
side scatter	polynomial 3. degree	$f(x) = 5.615 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot x^3 + -5.076 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot x^2 + 2.475 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot x + -0.041$
opacity	linear (fixed)	$f(x) = -0.17014 \cdot (1 - x)$
opacity	polynomial 3. degree	$f(x) = 6.0235 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot x^3 + -5.2991 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot x^2 + 0.27672 \cdot x + -0.072$
absorbance	hyperbolic	$f(x) = \frac{x}{2.2663 \cdot (0.3652 - x)}$

The root-mean-square error (*RMSE*) was used to evaluate the choice of models for the estimation of the biomass concentration. The formula for the *RMSE* is shown in Equation 5.7, where n is the amount of samples, y_i is the measured reference absorbance of sample i and \hat{y}_i is the predicted reference absorbance by the model with the sensor value of sample i . [82]

$$RSME = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (5.7)$$

5.2 Materials

Laboratory materials

Table 5.6: List of used consumables

Consumable	Name	Manufacturer
Cuvettes spectrophotometer (3 mL)	SARSTEDT 67.742	SARSTEDT AG & Co. KG, GER
Cuvettes flow-through cell (4.5 ml)	SARSTEDT 67.754	SARSTEDT AG & Co. KG, GER
silicone rubber for casting	type 3 HB	Troll Factory Rainer Habekost e.K., GER
PLA Filament for 3D printing	F10390 (matt black)	DAS FILAMENT, GER

Laboratory devices

Table 5.7: List of used laboratory devices

Consumable	Name	Manufacturer
Reference spectrophotometer	Libra S50	Biochrom Ltd, UK
Flask shaker	KS 260 basic	IKA®-Werke GmbH, GER
Gas mixing device	-	TCI
Peristaltic pump	iPump2S® YZ15A head	Signal Fluid, USA
3D printer	Prusa i3 MK3S+	Prusa Research, CZE
Infrared temperature sensor	P 4980	PeakTech GmbH, GER

Culture media

Bold's-Basal-medium (BBM)

Bolds-Basal-medium (BBM) was used to cultivate *C. vulgaris*. The original recipe can be found in [83]. It was prepared as described with the exception that no different vitamin concentrations were used. Furthermore, no additional soil was added. The components of the BBM medium are shown in Table 5.8.

Table 5.8: Components for preparation of BBM medium

Component	Concentration [mol L ⁻¹]
NaNO ₃	$2.94 \cdot 10^{-3}$
MgSO ₄ · 7 H ₂ O	$3.04 \cdot 10^{-4}$
NaCl	$4.28 \cdot 10^{-4}$
K ₂ HPO ₄	$4.31 \cdot 10^{-4}$
KH ₂ PO ₄	$1.29 \cdot 10^{-3}$
CaCl ₂ · 2 H ₂ O	$1.70 \cdot 10^{-4}$
ZnSO ₄ · 7 H ₂ O	$3.07 \cdot 10^{-5}$
MnCl ₂ · 4 H ₂ O	$7.28 \cdot 10^{-6}$
MoO ₃	$4.93 \cdot 10^{-6}$
CuSO ₄ · 5 H ₂ O	$6.29 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Co(NO ₃) ₂ · 6 H ₂ O	$1.68 \cdot 10^{-6}$
H ₃ BO ₃	$1.85 \cdot 10^{-4}$
EDTA · Na ₂	$1.71 \cdot 10^{-4}$
KOH	$5.53 \cdot 10^{-4}$
FeSO ₄ · 7 H ₂ O	$1.79 \cdot 10^{-5}$
FeSO ₄ · 7 H ₂ O	$1.79 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Thiamine	$3.77 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Biotin	$2.05 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Cyanocobalamin	$3.69 \cdot 10^{-10}$

Electronic sensor components

Table 5.9: List of key electronic components for sensor measurement

Component	Name	Manufacturer
LED 625 nm	H11A1-HR-30	Roithner Lasertechnik GmbH, AUT
LED 780 nm	ELD-780-524	Roithner Lasertechnik GmbH, AUT
LED 690 nm	LED690-03AU	Roithner Lasertechnik GmbH, AUT
LED 505 nm	B3B-443-B505	Roithner Lasertechnik GmbH, AUT
OPT-photodiode	OPT101P	Texas Instruments,USA
SD-photodiode	SD 112-45-11-221	Advanced Photonix, CA
ICP current source	M-7028 CR	ICPDAS-EUROPE GmbH, Ger
Black metal box current source	-	TCI
Propeller chip data logger	P8X32A	Parallax Inc., USA
Laptop	HP 250 G6, Windows 10 Pro	HP Inc., USA

Table 5.10: LED specifications

Component	Name	Half width	Viewing angle
LED 625 nm	H11A1-HR-30	20 nm	30°
LED 780 nm	ELD-780-524	28 nm	18°
LED 690 nm	LED690-03AU	25 nm	20°
LED 505 nm	B3B-443-B505	5 nm	15°

List of abbreviations and symbols

List of abbreviations

<i>A/D</i>	analog-to-digital
<i>BBM</i>	Bold's-Basal-medium
<i>C. vulgaris</i>	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>
<i>CSV</i>	comma-separated values
<i>e.g.</i>	for example
<i>Flask A</i>	specific shake flask cultivation of <i>C. vulgaris</i>
<i>Flask B</i>	specific shake flask cultivation of <i>C. vulgaris</i>
<i>HPLC</i>	high-performance liquid chromatography
<i>i.e.</i>	that is
<i>IR</i>	infra red (radiation)
<i>LED</i>	light-emitting diode
<i>NTU</i>	nephelometric turbidity units
<i>PBR1</i>	specific bioreactor cultivation of <i>C. vulgaris</i>
<i>PBR2</i>	specific bioreactor cultivation of <i>C. vulgaris</i>
<i>PLA</i>	polylactic acid
<i>PS</i>	polystyrene
<i>PTFE</i>	polytetrafluoroethylene

<i>TCI</i>	Institute of Technical Chemistry, LUH
<i>UV</i>	ultraviolet (radiation)
<i>V/V</i>	volume ratio
<i>Vis</i>	visible (radiation)

Indexverzeichnis

<i>blank</i>	of blank measurement
<i>BS</i>	of backscatter
<i>ink</i>	of original ink
<i>m</i>	of modes
<i>max</i>	maximum
<i>norm</i>	normalized to current
<i>S</i>	of scatter
<i>SS</i>	of side scatter
<i>stock</i>	of stock solution
<i>T</i>	of transmission

Symbolverzeichnis

λ	wavelength	[<i>m</i>]
\bar{x}	mean value	[<i>varies</i>]
σ	sample standard deviation	[<i>varies</i>]
θ	scatter angle	[<i>deg</i>]
ε	absorption coefficient	$\left[\frac{m^2}{kg}\right]$
<i>A</i>	absorbance	[–]
<i>F</i>	force	[<i>N</i>]
<i>I</i>	light intensity (also used as raw sensor signal [-])	$\left[\frac{W}{m^2}\right]$

l	light path length	[m]
n_B	repetitions of modes	[—]
O	opacity	[—]
r^2	coefficient of determination	[—]
$RMSE$	root-mean-square error	[<i>varies</i>]
T	transmittance	[—]
t	time	[s]
T'	relative transmittance	[—]
X	theoretical path until scatter event	[m]
c	concentration	[$\frac{kg}{m^3}$]

List of Figures

2.1	Ranges of electromagnetic radiation defined by their wavelength according to [23]. Adapted from [24].	3
2.2	Interactions of light with the particle of a sample inside a spectrophotometer cuvette shown from the upper view.	5
2.3	Oxygenic photosynthesis grouped by light and dark reactions [48].	9
3.1	Comparison of off-line UV-Vis wavelength scan experiment with <i>in vivo</i> pigment absorption data from literature.	20
3.2	Absorbance spectrum of diluted <i>C. vulgaris</i> samples at different cultivation times	23
3.3	Comparison between biomass related absorbance and normalized pigment related absorbances along two <i>C. vulgaris</i> shake flask cultivations	24
3.4	Schematic view of the measurement concept	29
3.5	Self-built flow-through cell	30
3.6	Basic structure of the sensor housing	32
3.7	Tension cap design	33
3.8	Complete sensor assembly	34
3.9	OPT-photodiode adapter	35
3.10	Flow chart diagram of the developed software for measurements with the new sensor.	38
3.11	Wavelength scan of ink measured with the reference spectrophotometer at different dilutions indicated by letters	41
3.12	Investigation of the side scatter and transmission signal of the newly developed sensor using ink at varying concentrations at 625 nm	43
3.13	Comparison between off-line spectrophotometric measurements and the off-line optical flow-through cell sensor measurements of ink absorbance at 625 nm	45

3.14	Side scatter and absorbance measured with the newly developed sensor at different formazin concentrations.	47
3.15	Backscatter signal of the newly developed sensor at different formazin concentrations	48
3.16	Monitoring of the growth of the <i>C. vulgaris</i> cultivation <i>PBR1</i> in a photobioreactor by different signals normalized to their maximum.	52
3.17	Fitting of the sensor signals of the 780 nm LED to the absorbance measured off-line with the spectrophotometer at 780 nm during cultivation <i>PBR1</i>	56
3.18	Testing of the biomass calibration curves previously obtained from cultivation <i>PBR1</i> on new data from cultivation <i>PBR2</i> of <i>C. vulgaris</i> in the photobioreactor	59
3.19	Estimation of time course of pigment content per biomass during cultivation <i>PBR2</i> of <i>C. vulgaris</i> in photobioreactor	62
3.20	Correlation between absorbance measured with the spectrophotometer and opacity measured with the on-line sensor, each related to the simultaneously measured value at 780 nm for two cultivations of <i>C. vulgaris</i> <i>PBR1</i> and <i>PBR2</i>	65
5.1	Scheme of the used photobioreactor system	76
5.2	Cultivation vessel setup.	77

List of Tables

2.1	State of the art optical sensors with multiple wavelengths for real-time monitoring of microalgae cultivations.	16
3.1	Comparison of the disturbing light intensity measured with side scatter and backscatter photodiode	50
5.1	List of ink concentrations	74
5.2	Sensor configuration of ink experiment	74
5.3	Sensor configuration of formazin experiment	75
5.4	Sensor configuration of monitoring in bypass of photobioreactor	78
5.5	List of regression formulas found in Figure 3.17.	79
5.6	List of used consumables	80
5.7	List of used laboratory devices	80
5.8	Components for preparation of BBM medium	81
5.9	List of key electronic components for sensor measurement	82
5.10	LED specifications	82

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